

Development of a DEM-Based Model for the Simulation of Fractures in Brittle Materials

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Abstract

This thesis introduces a model for simulating fracture in brittle continuum materials using the Discrete Element Method (DEM). The model employs either spheres or Voronoï cells approximated by multi-spheres to represent the material and uses beam forces that closely resemble Finite Element Method (FEM) matrix elastic frame elements to capture the interactions among them. The introduced beam forces allow us to integrate realistic failure criteria (like Mohr-Coulomb) and energy dissipation models (like Rayleigh damping), making it easy to employ real material parameters. The developed model successfully reproduces the elastic response of a metamaterial composed of glass beads connected by hardened glue bridges and the elastic and failure behavior of adobe bricks, a sustainable and affordable building material, and the simulation results are validated against experimental data. The brick model with Voronoï cells so developed can be used in the study of walls and other adobe structures and their potential applications as sustainable and affordable housing solutions, as well as the simulation of other brittle materials.

In addition to the model itself, this work introduces a novel integration algorithm for rotational motion that surpasses in accuracy, stability, and efficiency all existing algorithms used in state-of-the-art DEM codes and excels when integrating the motion of non-spherical particles, an algorithm with the potential to become a new standard in the field.

The work goes beyond material modeling and is a highly valuable contribution to the field of fracture modeling and the discrete element method in general.

Resumen

Esta tesis presenta un modelo para simular fractura en materiales frágiles continuos utilizando el Método de Elementos Discretos (DEM, por sus siglas en inglés). El modelo emplea esferas o celdas de Voronoï aproximadas mediante multi-esferas para representar el material y utiliza fuerzas en vigas que se asemejan a los elementos de pórtico elásticos de las matrices del Método de Elementos Finitos (FEM, por sus siglas en inglés) para capturar las interacciones entre ellas. Las fuerzas en vigas introducidas nos permiten integrar criterios realistas de falla (como Mohr-Coulomb) y modelos de disipación de energía (como amortiguamiento de Rayleigh), lo que facilita el uso de parámetros de materiales reales. El modelo desarrollado reproduce exitosamente la respuesta elástica de un metamaterial compuesto por canicas de vidrio conectadas por puentes de pegamento endurecido y el comportamiento elástico y de falla de ladrillos de adobe, un material de construcción sostenible y asequible, y los resultados de la simulación se validaron con datos experimentales. El modelo del ladrillo con celdas de Voronoï desarrollado se puede utilizar en el estudio de paredes y otras estructuras de adobe, así como en sus aplicaciones potenciales como soluciones de vivienda sostenibles y asequibles, al igual que en la simulación de otros materiales frágiles.

Además del modelo en sí, este trabajo presenta un algoritmo de integración novedoso para el movimiento rotacional que supera en precisión, estabilidad y eficiencia a todos los algoritmos existentes utilizados en los códigos de DEM actuales y destaca al integrar el movimiento de partículas no esféricas. El algoritmo tiene el potencial de convertirse en un nuevo estándar en el campo.

Este trabajo trasciende la modelización de materiales y constituye una contribución altamente valiosa al campo de la modelización de fracturas y al método de elementos discretos en general.

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Introduction

One of the oldest building materials is earth masonry [1], and adobe is the most common type [2]. In 1994, 30% of the world's population lived in homes made of earth masonry [3]. Adobe is a popular building material [4] due to its ability to bear heavy loads [5], its good thermal and acoustic properties [6], and its potential to be a more affordable [7] and sustainable [8, 9] alternative to concrete (which is the most widely produced material in the world [10], but also has a significant carbon footprint [11]). Nevertheless, adobe structures are known for being vulnerable to earthquakes and shear stresses [1, 12, 13] and, although adobe buildings can be seismically resistant using proper construction techniques [1, 2], the absence of unified building regulations limit its use as certified building material [14, 4]. Despite this, adobe's potential to improve the quality of life of homeless people by offering affordable households [15], improving infrastructure [16], and serving as environmentally sustainable building technology [17] - i.e. three of the Millennium Development Goals [18] - is an ideal subject of research. Numerical simulations are valuable tools to test adobe structures. However, accurately modeling the brittle behavior of adobe and similar materials poses challenges due to their heterogeneous structure and composition, [2, 5, 19, 20] plus the fact that material properties vary significantly with the fabrication process [21, 22, 23, 24, 25]. Moreover, simulating brittle materials asks for robust numerical methods capable of accurately capturing their dynamic behavior and fracture phenomena, which have posed challenges for numerous existing numerical techniques [26, 27]. Developing accurate models of brittle materials requires overcoming these challenges.

Many techniques have been used to simulate brittle fractures, both continuum and discrete. The first group includes the Finite Element Method (FEM) [23, 28], Multi-Point Method (MP), Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) [29, 30], and Phase-Field Model (PFM) [31, 32], whereas Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) [33], and Discrete Element Method (DEM) [34, 35, 36] are representative of the second group. On the one hand, continuum-based numerical methods excel at calculating material deformations [37]. But are computationally expensive [38], as they require multiple fields to represent deformations [33, 38], damage [37], and fracture zones within the mesh [28, 38]. They also struggle with contact interactions, dynamic situations, convergence

near fracture points [39], and extreme deformations [33, 39, 38]. On the other hand, discrete-based models are better at handling contact interactions and require only local interactions to simulate fractures [35]. In this approach, the material is modeled as a set of discrete particles with bound forces. Simulating continuum materials with DEM requires defining bond forces that reproduce the material’s solid mechanic behavior [34, 40]. Most DEM codes are designed for granular media, so only a few have implemented bonded models. For instance, MercuryDPM [41] has a model for liquid capillary bridges [42], YADE [43] includes beam elements to represent ropes or roots within granular media [44], and Mechsys can define beam forces along the common faces of adjacent spheropolyhedra [45]. It is worth noting that many DEM-bonded models for fracture barely use realistic failure criteria, like those used in mechanical and civil engineering, referring to the principal stresses of the bonds (Mohr-Coulomb, Rankine, von Mises, etc.).

This research aims to create a model and simulation framework to simulate fractures in brittle continuum materials like adobe. Our proposed model uses spheres bounded by beam elements to represent the elastic interactions inside the material. These beam elements feature twelve degrees of freedom, accounting for three-dimensional displacements and torsions as well as linear and angular velocities. This approach enables the calculation of the principal stresses of the beam elements, allowing the implementation of realistic failure criteria. This force model is sensitive to particle orientation and angular velocity, so an accurate integration of rotational motions is essential to maximize its effectiveness. Indeed, we developed a new rotational integration algorithm that is more precise and efficient than existing methods (see [section 6.3](#)). We have successfully integrated this algorithm into YADE [43], a popular DEM code, and a paper displaying the details of the algorithm has been written and is soon to be submitted. Furthermore, the DEM9 conference, to be held September 17th to 21st in Erlangen (Germany), [46] has accepted the author for an oral presentation on this algorithm.

To represent materials with the proposed beam-bonded spheres, we employed two approaches. The first one consists of representing the material as a collection of spheres connected by beams. In the second one, the material is modeled as a collection of Voronoï polyhedra represented as multi-spheres, and only spheres of the two polyhedra intersecting a common face can be connected with beams. This second method of modeling the material offers several advantages. Firstly, each polyhedron moves as a single discrete element and fewer beam elements are employed to bond them, resulting in improved simulation performance. Secondly, it eliminates the artificial planes that arise from the sphere packing structure. Moreover, the random nature of the Voronoï tessellations allows the model to account for variations in material properties and heterogeneities in its composition, i.e. structural randomness in a natural way.

The manuscript is organized as follows: In [chapter 2](#), we provide a background on masonry and adobe, emphasizing the significance of studying those materials and the challenges regarding their modeling and numerical simulations. Moving on to [chapter 3](#), we introduce some fundamental concepts of elasticity theory and delve into Hooke’s law. Additionally, we explore contact mechanics, focusing on Hertz’s force. Principal stresses and the theory behind Mohr circles are introduced in

[chapter 4](#), where we delve into the failure criterion employed in this work to represent brittle materials. Expanding on elasticity theory, [chapter 5](#) examines the underlying principles of elastic beams and introduces the beam elements that form the core of the force model presented in this study. Damping forces for the beam model are also addressed, and analytical derivations of the eigenmodes of elastic beam elements are provided. In [chapter 6](#), we discuss existing integration algorithms and specify the ones chosen for the simulations in this work. Furthermore, we develop a new algorithm for rotational motion and compare its performance against the currently employed methods. The details of the contact force model utilized in this work, including the new beam force model, are presented in [chapter 7](#), which also shows the implementation flexibility of the beam force model and provides implementation tips to enhance its performance. Validation cases of the model are presented in [chapter 8](#), also showcasing its capability to reproduce experimental results in a metamaterial with tunable elasticity [47] and exploring other potential applications. The simulations of adobe bricks and their comparison to experimental measurements, including simulation details, are outlined in [chapter 9](#). Finally, [chapter 10](#) encapsulates the conclusions drawn from this work, summarizing the achievements and contributions made throughout the research.

The model and algorithms developed in this work were initially implemented in our in-house Julia code before being integrated into YADE [43]. To make these advancements accessible to everyone, a merge request was submitted to include the new algorithm and model as part of the main YADE release. By doing so, we aim to provide a valuable contribution not only to the field of brittle fracture simulations but also to the DEM in general.

This work was partially founded by MSS and UNAL, see the Acknowledgments.

Adobe Masonry

”Earth is one of the oldest construction materials in use” [1], with adobe being the most common form of earth masonry [2]. Its origins date back to 8000 B.C. and it is considered one of the earliest known building materials [3]. Ancient structures in Jericho (6000 B.C.) and Chicama (3000 B.C.) were constructed using adobe [48]. Interestingly, some Roman constructions also incorporated adobe and are still standing today [19]. Shibam, a UNESCO World Heritage site, is known as the oldest skyscraper city and has buildings made of earth masonry over 30 meters tall [5]. Moreover, approximately 10% of UNESCO’s World Heritage sites consist of earth masonry constructions [49]. Although adobe buildings have existed for centuries, research suggests that the process of creating adobe has changed little for over 3000 years [50]. In 1994, approximately 30% of the world’s population lived in structures made from Earth-based materials [3]. A map showcasing the worldwide distribution of earth masonry structures can be seen in [Figure 2.1](#).

Figure 2.1: World distribution of earth-made buildings and seismic hazard. Taken from [4].

Adobe has historically been a popular construction material and is still widely used today. This is no coincidence. Adobe is cheap, recyclable, adaptable to various soil types, has good thermal and acoustic properties [6], and requires simple construction methods [51]. Adobe construction is also capable of withstanding significant loads. But if its strength is not enough, it can be reinforced by incorporating locally available materials, like fibers, straw, dry grass, sand, rice shells, and more [2, 5, 19, 6, 8, 50, 20].

Although adobe buildings have their advantages, they also present some challenges. One of these challenges is that the mechanical properties of adobe are affected by both the water content of the bricks and the manufacturing process. Additionally, the soils used to create the bricks are not homogeneous, meaning that two bricks made with the same mixture could have different mechanical properties, especially if biomaterials were added during the fabrication. Sensitivity to water content is particularly problematic in areas with high rainfall and frequent floods. To address these issues, various techniques have been proposed, such as considering the orientation of the building during construction. Another approach is to coat the bricks with limestone mixtures or to include other materials in the fabrication process [20, 52].

Adobe masonry structures face a significant challenge when it comes to earthquakes [1]. These buildings are not known for their seismic resistance, as demonstrated by the devastating effects of several earthquakes. For instance, in 2001, an earthquake with a magnitude of 8.4 in Arequipa, Moquegua, and Tacna destroyed 36,000 houses, 25,000 of them made of adobe. Two earthquakes happened in El Salvador the same year, with a magnitude of 7.7 and 6.6, which caused damage or the collapse of 200,000 adobe houses and the loss of 1,100 lives [53]. The 1976 Guatemala earthquake saw approximately 250,000 destroyed adobe houses, which caused about 98% of the total casualties [12]. The collapse mode of adobe structures consists of continuous tilting until the adobe blocks collapse [13], leaving little time for the residents to escape. Despite this, adobe constructions built with proper technique can be very strong [5] and even withstand earthquakes [1, 2].

Many countries have banned the construction of earth masonry houses due to safety concerns [14]. But, this is problematic as adobe is an affordable building material, and it is typical for people who cannot afford more expensive housing to use it anyway, engaging in illegal construction. Therefore, lack of building guidelines and proper regulation leads to unsafe buildings [14]. An example of the historical lack of regulations is Eurocode-6 [54], which features minimal guidelines for adobe. Another notable example is the Italian IBC 2008 code [55] and its complementary [56], which does not issue guidelines for earth masonry construction despite being very common in Italy. Note that there are codes that include building specifications for seismic-resistant masonry buildings [4]. For example, Colombia's AIS 610-EP-17 code [57]. Due to this dispersion of information in different regulations, the designer engineer or empiricist builder has to review multiple different guidelines, which can lead to information being misinterpreted or overlooked [58]. A possible solution is the creation of a unified code similar to Eurocode 6 for masonry structures, and Eurocode 8 for earthquake-resistant structures, which includes specific clauses for masonry [4].

There are benefits to promoting earth masonry buildings. Currently, the most commonly used materials in construction are concrete and steel [59]. However, concrete and aggregates, like gravel, make up the largest amount of human-made materials, surpassing all living biomass [10]. Additionally, producing concrete has a significantly high carbon footprint [11]. Therefore, using earth masonry bricks, which are cheaper and more eco-friendly, could result in more sustainable buildings and a good substitute for concrete [8, 7, 9]. It is important to note that the environmental and economic benefits may be reduced depending on the situation and the availability of materials [60]. Despite this, developments in adobe constructions have the potential to contribute to the Millennium Development Goals [18]. For example, improving the quality of life of homeless people by offering affordable households [15], improving infrastructure [16], and serving as environmentally sustainable building technology [17], three of the development goals.

As adobe is a widely used building material and varies so much with the building procedure, many efforts have been made to study and model it [23, 61, 62]. Computer simulations of adobe structures are a cheaper way of exploring material behavior under a wide range of situations. In [chapter 9](#), experimental measurements with the results of the simulations with the model presented in this work are available. As stated before, adobe material parameters vary significantly. To list a few, density reports range between 800 kg/m^3 [21] to 2000 kg/m^3 [22], Young modulus 10 MPa [23] to 200 MPa [24], and Poisson ratio 0.1 [61] to 0.3 [25].

Theory of Elasticity

The theory of elasticity is crucial for understanding how various materials behave under external forces [63]. The properties and behavior of different materials have significant implications in our daily lives, from constructing skyscrapers to aircraft and beyond [64]. Additionally, most solid materials exhibit some degree of elasticity, which is the focus of this chapter. Elastic deformation refers to the ability of a material to revert to its original shape after removing the force that caused the deformation [65]. That concept will lay the foundation of the force model proposed in this work.

Nevertheless, elasticity alone cannot account for all their behaviors [66]. We do not consider in this chapter cases where materials suffer damage or plastic deformation, but we will discuss energy dissipation caused by plastic deformation in section 3.3.

Despite the limitations of elasticity, it has countless applications in engineering and science and serves as the foundation for more complex theories [67]. We will explore some of the fundamental principles of elasticity in this chapter, and we will examine the concept of stress and strain and how they relate to elasticity. We will also look at Hooke's law, which describes the relationship between stress and strain in elastic materials and the parameters needed to describe it.

3.1 Basic Concepts

A few basic concepts are required to understand the follow-up theory. These concepts are the strain and stress tensors, the relevant material properties, and the fundamental elasticity equation.

3.1.1 Strain and Stress Tensor

Before speaking about tensors, let us dive into friction and pressure. The concept of pressure is very intuitive. We encounter pressure-related phenomena daily, for instance, when we feel the weight of an object in our hands or press our fingers against a hard surface. But, where does pressure come from?

In essence, pressure arises from electromagnetic repulsions among the electrons around atoms and molecules that make up matter [68]. As protons and electrons have electric charges, they create repulsive and attractive forces. These electric charges give rise to the delicate balance of forces governing the behavior of matter. A more formal way of defining pressure is the normal contact force exerted on a surface per unit area, meaning that it not only depends on how hard two objects are exerting forces on one other but also on how much of that object is involved in the contact. As we will discuss later, this is the origin of the stress tensor.

Figure 3.1: Representation of two rough surfaces in contact. When one of the surfaces moves, repulsion between the bumps will create resistance to the movement: friction.

However, contact forces have another component: friction. Friction has the same origin as pressure, but the overall effect it produces is different. Due to the rough nature of surfaces [69], little bumps repel each other creating resistance to tangent movement (see Figure 3.1); therefore, if the normal force between two objects increases, the effect of friction will too. Imagine the following situation: A person is carrying a glass of water in one hand. Naturally, as he holds it, it will not slip from his hand and shatter on the floor. But, if he reduces the grip strength, the glass will fall. Let us think of the free force diagram of the glass.

While drawing the free force diagram, the first forces that come to mind are the weight of the glass (which will go on the z -axis) and the force exerted by the hand on the x - y plane, perpendicular to the surface, which are the ones creating pressure. As we can assume that the force distribution is symmetric across the object, those forces will cancel each other. So, how hard the hold is, it does not affect the dynamics of the glass. Then, how is it that changing the force of the grip determines if the glass will fall or not? After all, intuition says it will. The answer is that we are missing the friction force in this analysis. Static friction is parallel to the surfaces and will act upwards, avoiding the surfaces to slide, and its value equals the weight, since this is the precise amount of force for the surfaces to be in relative rest. Nevertheless, its maximum static value grows proportional to the normal force, and if this normal force is too small the maximal static frictional force will not be enough to counteract the weight, and it will fall.

Friction is hard to model due to its nature. Before the surfaces start to slip, the magnitude of friction is smaller than the normal force times the static friction coefficient but big enough to

make tangent forces sum equal to zero. When the tangent forces surpass the maximum friction, the surface starts to slip, and the friction coefficient usually changes to a smaller value. In the slipping regime, the friction force is constant and equal to the normal times of the slipping friction coefficient (see [Figure 3.2](#)). The direction of the friction force is always opposite to the direction of relative tangential movement between the surfaces [\[70\]](#).

Figure 3.2: The behavior of the friction force magnitude as a function of external forces. μ_s is the static friction coefficient and μ_k is the kinetic or slipping coefficient. N is the normal force and F , the friction.

If we want to study in detail the forces acting on the object, we have to move on with the free force diagram and go a step further. To do this, let us divide the material into infinitesimally small pieces. Each piece has a normal vector representing its area $d\vec{A}$, and we would like to know the force exerted on that element. By convention, the vector points to the origin of the force (see [Figure 3.3](#)). The mathematical object that maps the area vector on the force is called the **stress tensor** [\[63\]](#). The stress tensor σ has pressure units and follows the relation in [Equation 3.1](#).

Figure 3.3: Graphical representation of an internal plane of the material where the stress tensor is being calculated. $d\vec{A}$ is the infinitesimal normal vector of area, $d\vec{F}$ is infinitesimal force vector, and P the point where the stress tensor is being evaluated.

$$dF_i = \sigma_{ij}dA_j. \quad (3.1)$$

Let us see an example. Consider a body that feels the same amount of pressure in all directions. This type of pressure is called hydrostatic because a body submerged in a fluid will feel the same pressure [65]. The hydrostatic stress tensor looks the following way

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} -p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -p \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.2)$$

Now that we understand how to model forces acting on a material, we need a way to explain how these forces will affect it, that is how can we describe the deformations they produce. Let us go along with a simple example. Consider a spring with one fixed end. The position vector of the free end is \vec{r} . If we elongate the spring, the new position vector is \vec{r}' . Then, the displacement vector is given by

$$\vec{u} = \vec{r}' - \vec{r}. \quad (3.3)$$

However, the displacement vector is not enough to describe the deformation of an object. For instance, if a square rotates, the corners will move but do not deform. In deformation, the distance between two points of the material must change. The distance between the initial and final point can be written in an infinitesimal form as

$$dl'^2 = dr_i'^2 = (dr_i + du_i)^2. \quad (3.4)$$

Substituting $du_i = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_k} dr_k$ we obtain

$$dl'^2 = dr_i^2 + 2 \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_k} dr_i dr_k + \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_k} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_l} dr_k dr_l. \quad (3.5)$$

Since the sum in the second term extends over both indices, we can write

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_k} dr_i dr_k = \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial r_i} dr_i dr_k. \quad (3.6)$$

Then, dl'^2 can be represented as

$$dl'^2 = dr_i^2 + 2\epsilon_{ik} dr_i dr_k, \quad (3.7)$$

where the tensor ϵ is the deformation or strain tensor [63], defined as

$$\epsilon_{ik} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_k} + \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial r_i} + \frac{\partial u_l}{\partial r_i} \frac{\partial u_l}{\partial r_k} \right) \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_k} + \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial r_i} \right). \quad (3.8)$$

By definition, it is a symmetric tensor. The approximation holds for small deformations.

3.1.2 Hooke's Law

When thinking about materials, we often recall their physical properties: strength, flexibility, durability, etc [68]. These properties are essential in determining how to use the material in several applications. Those properties could depend on many things, for instance: shape, composition, temperature, etc. Some materials even have different stiffnesses depending on the direction. These materials are called anisotropic, as opposed to isotropic materials.

Hooke's law is a simple model. It states that the force required to deform a spring of an isotropic material is proportional to the amount of deformation. In other words, it is a linear model. The proportionality constant is called the stiffness. Despite its simplicity, Hooke's law is the core of the theory of elasticity. Mathematically it can be written as [67]

$$\vec{F} = K \vec{\Delta r}. \quad (3.9)$$

It is worth mentioning that not all materials follow Hooke's law. Furthermore, Hooke's law is only valid within a range of deformations. When the material deforms beyond this range, it no longer follows the law and experiences plastic deformation or fracture. The limit of this range is called the elastic limit and depends on the material and its properties [66].

As mentioned earlier, the geometry of the material can affect the force required to deform it. For instance, a cylinder with a smaller radius will be easier to compress than one with a larger one. Therefore, stiffness alone is not enough to describe a material's behavior under stress and strain. We need to find parameters that are independent of the shape, i.e. Parameters that only depend on the composition of the object and not on the object itself.

3.1.3 Material Properties

To convert the stiffness from an extensive to an intensive property, we can multiply it by the length and divide it by the cross-section to find a quantity independent of the geometry. It is called Young's modulus or elastic modulus [68]. This new parameter is called Young's modulus is a measurement of the material's ability to resist deformation in response to an applied force. It has units of stress divided by strain (pressure units), where stress is the force applied to the material per unit area, and strain is the deformation per unit length. Young's modulus is a material property independent of the material's shape. Then, we can rewrite Equation 3.9 for tension or compression in terms of the Young modulus to get

$$\sigma_{ii} = E\epsilon_{ii}, \quad (3.10)$$

where E is the Young modulus.

However, one can expect that a material does not necessarily respond the same way to shearing as to compression or tension. A material subject to shear stress experiences deformation perpendicular to the applied force. Then, Equation 3.9 for a shearing deformation of an incompressible material is

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2G\epsilon_{ij}, \text{ for } i \neq j, \quad (3.11)$$

where G is the shear modulus.

The shear modulus, also known as the modulus of rigidity or elastic modulus in shear, measures the material's resistance to this type of deformation [68]. The shear modulus has units of stress divided by strain (same as the Young modulus). The shear and Young modulus are related to one another by the following expression

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}, \quad (3.12)$$

where ν is the Poisson ratio.

Poisson's ratio is a property of materials that describes how they deform under axial loads. It refers to the ratio of the transverse contraction strain to the longitudinal extension strain when an axial load is applied. This ratio is a dimensionless quantity ranging from -1 to 0.5. In isotropic materials, Poisson's ratio is always positive. This means that if we compress the material in one direction, it will tend to expand in the other two perpendicular directions. For example, if we elongate a rubber band in the x direction, the deformation in the y direction is given by

$$\epsilon_{yy} = -\nu\epsilon_{xx}. \quad (3.13)$$

Poisson's ratio essentially determines the proportion of these two strains.

3.1.4 The Fundamental Equation of Elasticity

Throughout the previous sections, we explored the behavior of elasticity. In the cases we examined, the relationship between the stress and strain tensors was linear, suggesting that stress and strain

are related in general by a linear combination represented by the elastic tensor C_{ijkl} as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\epsilon_{kl}. \quad (3.14)$$

This tensor has 36 components. Although, if the material has symmetry, not all the components are independent, and many are equal to zero. It is worth noting that in an isotropic material, there are only two independent elastic constants. In the isotropic case, there are only two ways to construct an isotropic tensor from another one linearly: multiplying by a constant and proportional to the trace:

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2\mu\epsilon_{ij} + \lambda Tr(\epsilon)\delta_{ij}, \quad (3.15)$$

where μ and λ are constants known as the Lamé parameters [71] and δ_{ij} is Kronecker's delta. Note that the trace of the strain tensor is a measurement of how compressible the material is

$$Tr(\epsilon) = \frac{\Delta V}{V}, \quad (3.16)$$

where V is the initial volume of the material. When this term is zero, the material is incompressible, then if $i \neq j$, $\mu = G$, arriving to Equation 3.11. If we consider the static equilibrium condition for an isotropic material

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma + \rho \vec{g} = 0, \quad (3.17)$$

and replace the definition of the strain tensor (Equation 3.8) into Equation 3.15, and then we replace this into the equilibrium condition, we find that the stress divergence is

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma = 2\mu \nabla \cdot \epsilon + \lambda \vec{\nabla} \cdot (Tr(\epsilon)\delta_{ij}). \quad (3.18)$$

To figure out what $\nabla \cdot \epsilon$ is, we can expand it for one component to start:

$$\begin{aligned} (\nabla \cdot \epsilon)_i &= \sum_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \epsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \sum_j \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_j}, \\ (\nabla \cdot \epsilon)_i &= \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 u_i + \frac{1}{2} \nabla_i (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

Doing the same procedure for the other components, we arrive at

$$\nabla \cdot \epsilon = \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \vec{u} + \frac{1}{2} \vec{\nabla} (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}). \quad (3.20)$$

The last term we are missing is $\vec{\nabla} \cdot (Tr(\epsilon)\delta_{ij})$. Let us expand it:

$$\begin{aligned} Tr(\epsilon) &= \epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy} + \epsilon_{zz} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = \nabla \cdot \vec{u} = \frac{\Delta V}{V}, \\ \vec{\nabla} \cdot (Tr(\epsilon)\delta_{ij}) &= \vec{\nabla} (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

Then, we finally arrive at the fundamental equation of elasticity under static equilibrium [63]:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \sigma + \rho \vec{g} &= 2\mu \left(\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \vec{u} + \frac{1}{2} \vec{\nabla}(\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) \right) + \lambda \vec{\nabla}(\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) + \rho \vec{g} = \mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} + (\mu + \lambda) \vec{\nabla}(\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) + \rho \vec{g} = 0. \\ \mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} + (\mu + \lambda) \vec{\nabla}(\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) + \rho \vec{g} &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{3.22}$$

This equation is known as the Lamé or Cauchy-Navier equation.

3.2 Hertz Force

In this section, we will scratch the surface of a field of elasticity called contact mechanics [69]. The objective is to describe the force between two elastic bodies in contact, in particular, focusing on the interaction between two elastic spheres. The force that describes this interaction is known as the Hertz force [72]. In this section, we will do a brief overview of its analytical derivation using the concepts of [section 3.1](#). The Hertz force model is crucial for simulations performed in this work, as it serves as one of the core forces in the model (see [chapter 7](#)).

Before discussing the force between two spheres, let us first consider the deformation caused by a point force F on an infinite elastic plane at $z = 0$ [63]. Using [Equation 3.22](#), the displacement of the surface is given by

$$\mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} + (\mu + \lambda) \vec{\nabla}(\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) = \vec{F} \delta(x) \delta(y), \tag{3.23}$$

where $\delta(x)$ is the Dirac delta function [73]. Although the solution to this equation is not interesting to this work, it can be used to create Green's function [74] of the Partial Differential Equation (PDE). Because the solution to the equation is $u_i = G_{ik}(x, y, z) F_{ik}$, then we can use this result to find the deformation caused by a force distribution $P(x, y)$ with the integral

$$u_i = \int G_{ik}(x - x', y - y', z - z') P_k(x', y'). \tag{3.24}$$

Then, consider two elastic spheres with radii R and R' , Young's moduli, and Poisson ratios E , E' , ν , and ν' , respectively. Let h be the interpenetration distance of the two spheres, which is the sum of their radii minus the distance between their centers. We define the positive z and z' directions to be towards the centers of their respective spheres. See [Figure 3.4](#).

Figure 3.4: Diagram of two overlapping spheres. z and z' are the directions for defining deformations, and h is the interpenetration.

Using the solution of Equation 3.23 and Equation 3.24 [63] and considering the contact surface flat, the deformation in the normal direction of each sphere is

$$\begin{aligned} u_z &= \frac{1 - \nu^2}{\pi E} \iint \frac{P_z(x', y')}{r} dx' dy'. \\ u'_z &= \frac{1 - \nu'^2}{\pi E'} \iint \frac{P_z(x', y')}{r} dx' dy'. \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

Note that the quotient of the deformations is

$$\frac{u_z}{u'_z} = \frac{(1 - \nu^2)E'}{(1 - \nu'^2)E}. \quad (3.26)$$

Also, the contact surface of the two spheres follows the relation [63]

$$Ax^2 + By^2 + u_z + u'_z = h, \quad (3.27)$$

where

$$A = B = \frac{1}{2R} + \frac{1}{2R'}. \quad (3.28)$$

The contact area between the two spheres is a circle. However, to be more general, assuming that the contact area between the two spheres is an ellipse, the pressure distribution must be of the form

$$P_x(x, y) = \text{const} \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2}}. \quad (3.29)$$

Choosing the constant so that the integral over of the pressure is equal to the total force, we find that

$$P_x(x, y) = \frac{3F}{2\pi ab} \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2}}. \quad (3.30)$$

As the integral over of the pressure follows the relation [63]

$$\iint \sqrt{1 - \frac{x'^2}{a^2} - \frac{y'^2}{b^2}} \frac{dx' dy'}{r} = \frac{\pi ab}{2} \int_0^\infty \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2 + \eta} - \frac{y^2}{b^2 + \eta}\right) \frac{d\eta}{\sqrt{(a^2 + \eta)(b^2 + \eta)\eta}}. \quad (3.31)$$

Replacing Equation 3.25, Equation 3.30 and Equation 3.31 in Equation 3.27, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{FD}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2 + \eta} - \frac{y^2}{b^2 + \eta} \right) \frac{d\eta}{\sqrt{(a^2 + \eta)(b^2 + \eta)\eta}} &= h - Ax^2 - By^2. \\ D &= \frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{1 - \nu^2}{E} + \frac{1 - \nu'^2}{E'} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

As this equation must hold for every value of x and y , we can separate it to find the coefficients. Solving for the interpenetration distance h , we get

$$\begin{aligned} h &= \frac{FD}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{d\eta}{\sqrt{(a^2 + \eta)(b^2 + \eta)\eta}} = F^{2/3} \left(D^2 \left(\frac{1}{R} + \frac{1}{R'} \right) \right)^{1/3}. \\ A &= \frac{FD}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{d\eta}{(a^2 + \eta)\sqrt{(a^2 + \eta)(b^2 + \eta)\eta}}. \\ B &= \frac{FD}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{d\eta}{(b^2 + \eta)\sqrt{(a^2 + \eta)(b^2 + \eta)\eta}}. \\ a &= F^{1/3} \left(\frac{DRR'}{R + R'} \right)^{1/3}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

To reach the result for h , we first solved the integrals for the coefficients A and B and used Equation 3.28 to calculate the radius of the contact circle ($a = b$). Then, replaced the result in the expression for h . From this expression, we can solve for the force to find that the Hertz force is

$$F = \frac{4}{3} E^* \sqrt{R^*} h^{3/2}, \quad (3.34)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{E^*} &= \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E} + \frac{1 - \nu'^2}{E'}. \\ \frac{1}{R^*} &= \frac{1}{R} + \frac{1}{R'}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

Studies that compare Hertz force with the force from FEM simulations have found that deformation needs to be smaller than 12 % of the particle diameter for the Hertz force accurate [75].

3.3 Restitution Coefficient

In the previous sections, we learned about how elastic bodies behave and the fundamental force model for contact mechanics. A perfectly elastic material can return to its original shape and size after being stretched or compressed, but in reality, all materials suffer some degree of energy loss during deformation [69]. For example, when an elastic ball bounces on the ground, it falls to a lower point with each bounce. See Figure 3.5. Several things happen during each impact between the ball and the floor. The ball and the floor slightly plastically deform, and the pressure

waves that travel inside the ball dissipate some of their energy as heat. Then, if we want to model many bouncing bodies, we need to know how to incorporate this effect [76]. Hertz force alone can not reproduce experimental results [77]. Therefore, finding the dissipative force that describes the contact between two elastic objects is of great importance for the simulations in this work. See [chapter 7](#).

Figure 3.5: Graph of the height against the time of the simulation of a bouncing glass marble on a glass surface. The marble has a diameter of 1.3 cm. Glass density is 2.5 g/cm^3 , Young modulus is $E = 65 \text{ GPa}$, and poisson ratio is $\nu = 0.22$ [78]. The glass-on-glass friction coefficient is $\mu = 0.4$ [79]. The restitution coefficient is $e_n = 0.92$ [80] and, in this case, is assumed constant, see [chapter 7](#).

To describe contact energy dissipation, we use the coefficient of restitution. Its defined as [81]

$$e_n = \frac{V'}{V}. \quad (3.36)$$

V is the velocity before and V' is the velocity after impact. Then, the coefficient of restitution is the ratio between these two velocities. Another way of defining the coefficient is as follows:

$$e_n = \sqrt{\frac{h_f}{h_0}}, \quad (3.37)$$

where h_0 and h_f are the initial and final heights after one bounce. We need to find an expression that describes the force as a function of the restitution coefficient. Regardless, doing this is not

easy analytically. Additionally, it is challenging to perform experimental studies on this topic due to the numerous external factors. For example, forces like surface forces, plastic deformation, and adhesion [82] can influence the results. Therefore, many of these models are created by fitting data from numerical simulations and contrasting them with experimental data [81]. In [chapter 7](#) a more in-depth discussion about the different force models is available.

Theory of Fracture

When materials fail, they can either fracture (like brittle materials) or experience plastic deformation (like ductile materials) before ultimately breaking [66]. Understanding how both types of materials fail is crucial for predicting material failure. Unfortunately, there is no universal failure theory. Instead, we need to choose the most suitable for each type of material. In this chapter, we will review some of the most common failure theories and see the main difference between brittle and ductile material failure. Also, this chapter will introduce a powerful tool for studying fractures and, in general, stresses in a material, the Mohr circles [83].

4.1 Principal Stresses

To start, let us recap from subsection 3.1.1. The internal stress in a material can be described with the stress tensor. However, not all stresses create the same effect. In subsection 3.1.1, we saw that stresses that compress or expand the body the same amount from all directions are called hydrostatic stresses in analogy to the pressure experienced by an object submerged in a fluid. Hydrostatic stress does not modify the shape of materials. The stresses that do change the geometry are called deviatoric stresses. A good question is how to identify these stresses in the stress tensor. One way is to separate the stress tensor into two: a hydrostatic and a deviatoric component.

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \sigma_y & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \sigma_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{avg} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{avg} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{avg} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x - \sigma_{avg} & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \sigma_y - \sigma_{avg} & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \sigma_z - \sigma_{avg} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.1)$$

where σ_{avg} is the average stress. The first term is the hydrostatic component, and the second is the deviatoric component. However, this equation can be written in a simpler way in the principal stress frame. Due to the symmetric nature of the stress tensor, it is diagonalizable by orthogonal

matrices. Then, we can always find a transformation Q such that [84]

$$\Sigma = Q^T \sigma Q, \quad (4.2)$$

where Σ is a diagonal matrix. The transformation also represents a rotation of the reference frame. Then, the stresses in the new reference frame are called principal stresses, and Equation 4.1 can be rewritten as

$$\sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{avg} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{avg} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{avg} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 - \sigma_{avg} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2 - \sigma_{avg} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_3 - \sigma_{avg} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.3)$$

where σ_i are the principal stresses. It is a widely accepted practice to arrange the stresses in descending order. In the present study, we attach to this convention. Therefore

$$\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \sigma_3. \quad (4.4)$$

4.2 Mohr Circles

Mohr circles were introduced by Mohr in 1866 [85] and have since become an essential tool for understanding the behavior of materials under different stress conditions [83]. Their origin comes from the internal friction of a material. See section 3.1. Consider the setup in Figure 3.3. Integrating Equation 3.1 we get

Figure 4.1: Mohr circles and the principal stresses. σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_3 are the principal stresses. σ_{avg} is the average stress and measures the hydrostatic stress acting on the object. The radius of the biggest Mohr circle is the deviatoric stress acting on the object.

$$F_i = \sigma_{ij} A_j. \quad (4.5)$$

Let us define a unitary vector \hat{n} in the direction of the vector \vec{A} . Then we can calculate

$$f_i = \sigma_{ij} n_j, \quad (4.6)$$

where \vec{f} has a normal and a tangent component to the plane. The goal is to find the relationship between those components for every possible direction of \hat{n} . To do this, we will consider the stress tensor to be in the principal stress frame

$$\vec{f} = \sigma \cdot \hat{n} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} n_x \\ n_y \\ n_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 n_x \\ \sigma_2 n_y \\ \sigma_3 n_z \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.7)$$

$$n_x^2 + n_y^2 + n_z^2 = 1.$$

$$f^2 = f_{\parallel}^2 + f_{\perp}^2 = \sigma_1^2 n_x^2 + \sigma_2^2 n_y^2 + \sigma_3^2 n_z^2,$$

where n_i are the components of the normal vector, f_{\parallel} is the tangent component of the force to the plane, and f_{\perp} is the normal component. We can write the normal component as

$$f_{\perp} = \vec{f} \cdot \hat{n} = \sigma_1 n_x^2 + \sigma_2 n_y^2 + \sigma_3 n_z^2. \quad (4.8)$$

Using the fact that $n_z^2 = 1 - n_x^2 - n_y^2$ and replacing in f_\perp and the expression for $f_\parallel^2 + f_\perp^2$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} f_\perp - \sigma_3 &= (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)n_x^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)n_y^2. \\ f_\perp^2 + f_\parallel^2 - \sigma_3^2 &= (\sigma_1^2 - \sigma_3^2)n_x^2 + (\sigma_2^2 - \sigma_3^2)n_y^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

To eliminate n_y^2 , multiply the first equation by $(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)$ and subtract the second one to get

$$f_\parallel^2 + f_\perp^2 - (\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)f_\perp = (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)n_x^2 - \sigma_2\sigma_3. \quad (4.10)$$

Adding $\left(\frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2$ to both sides to complete squares we end up with

$$f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 + (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)n_x^2. \quad (4.11)$$

It is clear that due to symmetry, repeating the process for n_x^2 and n_y^2 will yield an analogous result. Then, using [Equation 4.4](#) we find

$$\begin{aligned} f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 &= (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)n_x^2 > 0. \\ f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 &= (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1)n_y^2 < 0. \\ f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2}{2}\right)^2 &= (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)(\sigma_3 - \sigma_2)n_z^2 > 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

Rearranging these equations

$$\begin{aligned} f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 &> \left(\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2. \\ f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2 &< \left(\frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2}\right)^2. \\ f_\parallel^2 + \left(f_\perp - \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}{2}\right)^2 &> \left(\frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2}{2}\right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

These equations describe a region in space inside a circle excluding two smaller circles that are inside, the region in green in [Figure 4.1](#). Those three circles are Mohr circles. Mohr circles are a graphical way to visualize the stresses acting on a material. For example, note in [Equation 4.3](#) that the hydrostatic stress is σ_{avg} . As shown in the figure, an increase in hydrostatic pressure shifts Mohr's circles to the right. In the same way, an increase in deviatoric stress appears as an increase in the circle's radius without changing the average stress. Furthermore, the radius of the big circle is the deviatoric stress experienced by the object [85].

Figure 4.2: Difference between uniaxial tensile and compressive tests in brittle materials. $\sigma_{u,t}$ is the ultimate tensile strength and $\sigma_{u,c}$ the ultimate compressive strength.

Figure 4.3: Comparison between a brittle and ductile material tensile uniaxial test. $\sigma_{u,t}$ is the ultimate tensile strength and σ_y the yield strength.

4.3 Failure Criteria

We know that if we keep loading a material, it will ultimately fail. In ductile materials, failure occurs when the material undergoes plastic deformation, while in brittle materials, failure occurs at fracture. Uniaxial tests make it easy to identify the failure. In this case, failure happens when the normal stresses of the object reach the yielding strength in ductile materials, or the ultimate strength in brittle materials, as shown in Figure 4.3. However, predicting failure in more complex triaxial stress situations is not straightforward. As discussed earlier in this chapter, a universal failure theory does not exist. As a result, we have to select the most suitable one for the given situation. Most failure theories are defined as a function of the principal, yield, and ultimate stresses.

Figure 4.4: Yield surface of Von Mises and Mohr-Culomb failure criteria. In red, Von Mises yield surface. In blue, Mohr-Culomb yield surface. σ_y is the yield strength, and $\sigma_{u,c}$ and $\sigma_{u,t}$ are the ultimate compression and tensile strengths.

When considering the observed behavior of ductile materials under stress, it is important to note that hydrostatic stress does not cause yielding. Deviatoric stress does cause yielding. In brittle materials, both types of stress can cause a fracture. Also, brittle materials tend to have much larger compressive strengths than tensile strengths. Therefore, we need to know the two ultimate stresses. See Figure 4.2. A good failure theory must be consistent with these observations.

One of the most popular failure criteria for ductile materials is the Von misses or maximum distortion energy theory. The theory states that yielding occurs when the maximum distortion energy is the distortion energy at yielding in a uniaxial tensile test ($u_d = u_{d,y}$). The distortion energy is the portion of strain energy corresponding to the effect of the deviatoric stresses and can be calculated with

$$u_d = \frac{1 + \nu}{6E} ((\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2). \quad (4.14)$$

We know that at yielding, during a tensile test, the maximum principal stress is equal to the yield

strength of the material, and the other two are equal to zero (see [Figure 4.5](#)). Then the distortion energy at yielding is

$$u_{d,y} = \frac{1 + \nu}{6E} \sigma_y^2. \quad (4.15)$$

Then, the failure occurs when

$$\sigma_y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} ((\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2)}. \quad (4.16)$$

Note that the theory considers the difference between the principal stress, then its independent of hydrostatic stress. A way of visualizing the theory is by plotting the yield surface. The yield surface is the representation of a failure theory in the principal stress space. If we set σ_3 to a constant value, for example, zero, we can see the region in the plane where the theory predicts failure. The yield surface of the Von Mises theory can be seen in [Figure 4.4](#).

Figure 4.5: Mohr circle diagram of a tensile and compressive test at yielding for a brittle material and Mohr-Coulomb failure criteria. $\sigma_{u,c}$ and $\sigma_{u,t}$ the ultimate compression and tensile strengths.

A popular theory for predicting failure in brittle materials is the Mohr-Coulomb theory. This theory is suitable for brittle materials, as it accounts for the sensitivity of failure to hydrostatic stress and the difference between compressive and tensile strengths. According to the Coulomb-Mohr theory, failure occurs when the Mohr circle of the material intersects with the envelope created by the tangent line to the Mohr circles corresponding to uniaxial tensile and compressive tests at yielding. This envelope is illustrated in [Figure 4.5](#). The yield surface of the theory can be observed

in [Figure 4.4](#). Mathematically, the Mohr-Culomb theory is given by

$$\tau = c + \sigma \tan \phi, \quad (4.17)$$

where c is the cohesion and ϕ is the angle of internal friction. In terms of the ultimate strengths:

$$\begin{aligned} \sin \phi &= \frac{\sigma_{u,c} - \sigma_{u,t}}{\sigma_{u,c} + \sigma_{u,t}}, \\ c &= \frac{\sigma_{u,c}\sigma_{u,t}}{(\sigma_{u,c} + \sigma_{u,t})\sqrt{-\frac{(\sigma_{u,c}-\sigma_{u,t})^2}{(\sigma_{u,c}+\sigma_{u,t})^2} + 1}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.18)$$

where $\sigma_{u,c}$ is the ultimate compression strength and $\sigma_{u,t}$ is the ultimate tensile strength. It is important to note that the values of ϕ and c are usually determined experimentally, not calculated in this way. Also, note that in [Figure 4.4](#), [Figure 4.5](#), [Figure 4.2](#), and [Figure 4.3](#), the compressive stress is assumed negative. This is just a convention and can be inverted if necessary.

Elastic Beam Model

In the previous section, we provided the foundation for understanding the behavior of elastic materials. However, the structural aspects of these materials are necessary at the time of calculating forces and deformations. This chapter will focus on elastic beams and frames, which play a crucial role in the force model proposed in this work (see section [chapter 7](#)).

5.1 Euler Bernoulli Beam

Elastic beams are critical structural elements in numerous applications. One of the most commonly used models for analyzing beam behavior is the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory [64]. In this section, we will review this theory.

The Euler-Bernoulli beam theory assumes that all deformations are elastic, allowing for the calculation of deflection, bending moment, and shear force distribution along the beam.

Figure 5.1: Diagram showing a beam element's shear and bending moments. The image is courtesy of Prof. José Daniel Muñoz and is part of his course in Fluids and Elasticity.

When a beam deforms, one side compresses, and the other one expands. Creating a shear force

and a bending moment, as shown in Figure 5.1. For a beam aligned with the x-axis, these are

$$\begin{aligned} M(x) &= - \int \int y \sigma_{xx}(y) dy dz. \\ V(x) &= \int \int \sigma_{xy}(y) dy dz. \end{aligned} \tag{5.1}$$

Under a static condition, ie.

$$\sum_i \vec{F}_i = \sum_i \vec{\tau}_i = 0, \tag{5.2}$$

the equations for the shear and moment can be written in differential form as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV}{dx} &= w(x), \\ \frac{dM}{dx} &= V(x), \end{aligned} \tag{5.3}$$

where $w(x)$ are the external forces acting in the beam. For example, it is weight. From these equations, we can find a differential equation that describes the deflection of the beam [64]

$$EI \frac{d^4 \eta}{dx^4} = w(x). \tag{5.4}$$

This is the Euler-Bernoulli equation for beams where E is the Young Modulus and I the second moment of area and it is defined as

$$I = \int \int y^2 dy dz. \tag{5.5}$$

Using this equation we can calculate the deflection of beams. For example for a beam in a cantilever (see Figure 5.2). A beam in a cantilever has one of its ends fixed and that end cannot rotate. Let us assume that its weight is the only external force acting upon it.

Figure 5.2: Diagram of the deflection in a cantilever beam. In black the beam before deforming and in blue the beam after it deformed.

Then, for a beam of length L and mass m , the boundary conditions and the differential equations

are

$$\begin{aligned}
 EI \frac{d^4 \eta}{dx^4} &= -mg/L. \\
 \eta(0) &= 0, \quad \eta'(0) = 0. \\
 \eta''(L) &= M(L) = 0, \quad \eta'''(L) = V(L) = 0.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5.6}$$

To solve this equation, we can propose a polynomial solution. Since the equation states that the fourth derivative of a polynomial is a constant, the polynomial must be a fourth-order polynomial. We can then substitute the polynomial into the equation and apply the boundary conditions to calculate the coefficients

$$\eta(x) = -\frac{mgx^2}{EI} \left(\frac{x^2}{24L} - \frac{x}{6} + \frac{L}{4} \right).
 \tag{5.7}$$

There are other beam theory approximations. For example, Timoshenko Beam Theory [67]. However, it is not easy to find analytical solutions using these theories in many cases. Then, equations need to be solved numerically.

5.2 Beam Principal Stresses

In Chapter 4, we saw the crucial role of the principal stresses in determining fractures. Therefore, we need to know how to calculate the principal stresses in beams. It is important to note that beams can be affected by both deformation and twisting, and the moments acting on the beam will also contribute to the stress. See Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3: Shear and Moment force contributions to the stresses in a Beam. Taken from [86].

Assuming that the beam is aligned with the x-axis and subjected to shear and moments in all

directions, the principal stresses for the beam cross-section can be expressed as [86]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_1 &= \frac{\sigma_x}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{2}\right)^2 + (\tau_y^2 + \tau_z^2)}. \\ \sigma_3 &= \frac{\sigma_x}{2} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{2}\right)^2 + (\tau_y^2 + \tau_z^2)}.\end{aligned}\tag{5.8}$$

For a circular beam cross-section ($\frac{4}{3}$ factor)

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= \frac{V_x}{A} + \frac{M_y}{S} + \frac{M_z}{S}. \\ \tau_y &= \frac{4V_y}{3A}. \\ \tau_z &= \frac{4V_z}{3A} + \frac{M_x}{S},\end{aligned}\tag{5.9}$$

where A is the area of the cross-section, and S is the Section modulus. For a beam with a circular cross-section with radius r and second moment of area I , is defined as

$$S = \frac{I}{r}.\tag{5.10}$$

5.3 Beam Matrix Analysis

We saw that to describe the force and torque acting on an elastic beam based on its deformation, a differential equation needs to be solved. Solving this equation numerically can be computationally expensive. One way of avoiding this task is to linearize the differential equation using the same approach as in Finite Element Method (FEM) [87]. This way, the equation is simplified into a matrix multiplication, making the calculation much faster. When working with many bodies connected with beams, as in this work, the performance gains are crucial. Note that what we refer to as beam elements and beam forces is what is commonly known as space frames and frame forces in civil engineering.

Let us consider a beam with two nodes. The beam is aligned with the x-axis and has its reference frame at the center. If the nodes move or rotate, the beam will respond accordingly. Let \vec{X} be a vector that contains the movements and rotations with respect to the beam of each node. The first six elements are the displacements and twisting angles of the first node, and the other six are the displacements and angles of the second node. Then the force and torque acting on each node are given by

$$\vec{F} = K\vec{X},\tag{5.11}$$

where \vec{F} is a 12-entry vector representing external forces and torques acting on the two nodes. K is the 12x12 stiffness matrix. The first six entries of \vec{F} represent the forces and torques acting on the first node, and the remaining six entries correspond to the second node.

In the case of an elastic beam, properties such as the length in equilibrium remain constant,

then the stiffness matrix is also constant on time. The matrix can be calculated using the material properties and the geometry of the beam. The stiffness matrix is given by [88]

$$K = \frac{E}{L^3} \begin{pmatrix} K_{jj} & K_{jk} \\ K_{kj} & K_{kk} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.12)$$

where

$$K_{jj} = \begin{pmatrix} L^2 A & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 12I_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6LI_z \\ 0 & 0 & 12I_y & 0 & -6LI_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{G}{E}L^2 J & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -6LI_y & 0 & 4L^2 I_y & 0 \\ 0 & 6LI_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4L^2 I_z \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$K_{kk} = \begin{pmatrix} L^2 A & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 12I_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & -6LI_z \\ 0 & 0 & 12I_y & 0 & 6LI_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{G}{E}L^2 J & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 6LI_y & 0 & 4L^2 I_y & 0 \\ 0 & -6LI_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4L^2 I_z \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.13)$$

$$K_{kj} = \begin{pmatrix} -L^2 A & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -12I_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & -6LI_z \\ 0 & 0 & -12I_y & 0 & 6LI_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{G}{E}L^2 J & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -6LI_y & 0 & 2L^2 I_y & 0 \\ 0 & 6LI_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2L^2 I_z \end{pmatrix}.$$

Here, A is the area of the cross-section, L is the length of the beam, I_y and I_z are the corresponding second moments of area, G is the shear modulus, E is the Young modulus, and J is the torsional constant of the cross-section. For a beam with a circular cross-section with radius r , the second moment of area is given by

$$I_y = I_z = \frac{\pi}{4} r^2. \quad (5.14)$$

The torsional constant is defined as

$$J = \frac{\pi}{2} r^4 \quad (5.15)$$

In the same way as the stiffness matrix, we can calculate the mass matrix with [64]

$$M = \frac{\rho AL}{420} \begin{pmatrix} M_{jj} & M_{jk} \\ M_{kj} & M_{kk} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.16)$$

where

$$M_{jj} = \begin{pmatrix} 140 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 156 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 22L \\ 0 & 0 & 156 & 0 & -22L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 140r_g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -22L & 0 & 4L^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 22L & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4L^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$M_{kk} = \begin{pmatrix} 140 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 156 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -22L \\ 0 & 0 & 156 & 0 & 22L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 140r_g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 22L & 0 & 4L^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -22L & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4L^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.17)$$

$$M_{kj} = \begin{pmatrix} 70 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 54 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 13L \\ 0 & 0 & 54 & 0 & -13L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 70r_g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 13L & 0 & -3L^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -13L & 0 & 0 & 0 & -3L^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Here ρ is the beam density and r_g is the radius of gyration of the cross-section and is defined as

$$r_g = \sqrt{\frac{I_x}{A}}. \quad (5.18)$$

$$I_x = \frac{2}{3}Lr^3.$$

Using those matrices, we can calculate the modes of oscillation of the structure by solving the eigenvalue problem [64]

$$K = \omega^2 M. \quad (5.19)$$

In the next section, it will become clear why this equation holds for a purely elastic structure.

5.4 Rayleigh Damping

In the previous section, we learned about using matrices to model elastic beams. However, not all materials behave purely elastically. Even highly elastic materials experience energy dissipation due to deformation-induced heating. Thus, to represent real materials, we need to extend our approach to beams, as we did when simulating sphere collisions in [section 3.3](#). Additionally, as we have to model fracture in our simulations, we require damping to maintain the simulation stability. Since we are using matrices to model beams, we need to incorporate damping in a compatible way, also as a matrix. We can achieve this by proposing a damping force that is proportional to the velocity of the modes, as follows:

$$M\ddot{U} = D\dot{U} + KU, \quad (5.20)$$

where M and K are the mass and stiffness matrices, respectively, while D is the damping matrix. In this section, we will construct the damping matrix. To do it, let us start by solving the differential equation. proposing a solution of the form $U = \beta e^{\omega t}$, we arrive at the equation

$$\omega^2 M + \omega D + K = 0, \quad (5.21)$$

where ω , as we are dealing with a matrix equation, is a vector of eigenvalues. Note that doing the same procedure for a case without damping yields [Equation 5.19](#). The eigenvalues are the roots of a $2N$ order polynomial. Then, the general solution to the equation is

$$U = \sum_{n=1}^{2N} a_n \beta_n e^{\omega_n t}. \quad (5.22)$$

To obtain the damping matrix, we could attempt to solve the quadratic eigenvalue problem directly. However, this can prove computationally challenging. As an alternative, we can assume modal damping, where each eigenmode is affected separately by a specified damping coefficient. This assumption holds when the vibration modes without damping are orthogonal to the damping matrix [\[64\]](#). Then, a damping matrix that satisfies this constraint is proportional to the mass or the stiffness matrix. Or, to be more general, a linear combination of the two. Using this approach, we can construct a proportional damping matrix.

Let us start considering a mass-proportional damping

$$D = a_0 M. \quad (5.23)$$

In this case, it can be shown that the coefficient is

$$a_0 = 2\zeta_n \omega_n. \quad (5.24)$$

Here, ζ_n represents the modal damping corresponding to the eigenvalue ω_n . When selecting which eigenvalue of a structure to use, it is usual to choose the most significant one. In other words, the

eigenvalue that excites the most amount of mass in the system. Similarly, for stiffness-proportional damping, we find

$$\begin{aligned} D &= a_1 K. \\ a_1 &= \frac{2\zeta_n}{\omega_n}. \end{aligned} \tag{5.25}$$

As stated before, a linear combination of the mass and stiffness matrices also satisfies also the orthogonality condition:

$$D = a_0 M + a_1 K. \tag{5.26}$$

To find the coefficients in this case we need to specify the modal damping of two eigenmodes. Then, by setting them equal, $\zeta_n = \zeta_m = \zeta$ (which is a reasonable assumption [64]) we find

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= \frac{2\zeta\omega_n\omega_m}{\omega_n + \omega_m}. \\ a_1 &= \frac{2\zeta}{\omega_n + \omega_m}. \end{aligned} \tag{5.27}$$

This proportional damping created by the linear combination of the stiffness and mass matrices is known as Rayleigh damping [64]. In the simulations conducted in this work, we use this damping model. Given a modal damping, we can see how these different damping models dampen the other frequencies (see Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4: Damping ratio versus frequency for Rayleigh damping. Here, $\omega_0 = 3$, $\omega_1 = 6$, $\zeta = 0.1$.

5.5 Elastic Beam Eigenmodes

In 5.4, we discussed the importance of identifying the frequency of oscillation that needs to be dampened. If the frequency is unknown, we can use Equation 5.19. However, it is common to solve

it numerically with an eigenvalue solver. Nevertheless, we discovered that this equation can also be solved analytically, which is a small but valuable finding, although it may not be novel. With the assistance of SageMath [89], we were able to determine the solution to the eigenvalue problem presented in Equation 5.19.

$$\left[\frac{720 EI_z}{AL^4\rho}, \frac{8400 EI_z}{AL^4\rho}, \frac{720 EI_y}{AL^4\rho}, \frac{8400 EI_y}{AL^4\rho}, \frac{12 GJ}{IxL^2\rho}, \frac{12 E}{L^2\rho}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0 \right] \quad (5.28)$$

It is not surprising that the system exhibits only six eigenmodes. After all, the twelve degrees of freedom are paired, resulting in six distinct modes. Hence, we can select the two smallest eigenmodes to construct the Rayleigh damping matrix.

Integration of Motion

The integration algorithm is crucial for DEM simulation as it updates the velocities, positions, angular velocities, and orientations of particles and objects based on the equations of motion. To do this, it calculates the forces and torques acting on each element and predicts with them the new positions and velocities. This is repeated at every time step. This ensures the simulation progresses in time, and the system evolution remains consistent with physics. As the equations of motion cannot be solved analytically for a general case, numerical methods must be used. In this section, we will evaluate and discuss some of these methods. Furthermore, during this work, we developed an algorithm for rotational motion superior to existing algorithms.

6.1 Translation algorithms

The goal of a translational integration algorithm is to provide a numerical solution to Newton's second law of motion [70]. Specifically

$$\vec{F} = m \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \vec{r}. \quad (6.1)$$

where \vec{F} is the force acting on the body, and m its mass. Note that the mass is assumed to be constant.

The most common way to go about it is to divide the second-order equation into a system of two first-order equations as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F} &= m \frac{d}{dt} \vec{v}, \\ \vec{v} &= \frac{d}{dt} \vec{r}, \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

where \vec{v} is the velocity. Then, the easiest way to solve it is to use a first-order approximation using

the direct Euler's method [90]:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{v}(t + dt) &= \vec{v}(t) + \frac{dt}{m} \vec{F}(t) + O(dt^2), \\ \vec{r}(t + dt) &= \vec{r}(t) + \vec{v}(t)dt + O(dt^2).\end{aligned}\tag{6.3}$$

However, this algorithm requires incredibly small time steps to yield good results. Therefore, using it in a DEM simulation is not viable. Nonetheless, some state-of-the-art DEM codes like Mfix [91], EDEM [92], and BlazeDEMGPU [93] still use Direct Euler as their main integration scheme to achieve the maximum performance possible. However, they sacrifice stability and accuracy.

There are countless better integration algorithms. Some of the most popular algorithms are Verlet [94], its variations [95][96], and the leapfrog algorithm [97]. This work uses the leapfrog algorithm for compatibility with the chosen rotation algorithm.

The leapfrog algorithm is popular due to its easy implementation and efficiency. Also, it is cheap to perform as it only requires one force computation and does not present numerical instabilities. It features a third-order approximation in the position and the velocity and is symplectic. Symplectic means that the conservation of energy is guaranteed. To derive the algorithm, let's expand on a Taylor series the position at times t and $t + dt$ around $t + dt/2$:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{r}(t) &= \vec{r}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2} - \frac{dt}{2}\right) \approx \vec{r}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) - \frac{dt}{2} \vec{v}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dt}{2}\right)^2 \vec{a}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + O(dt^3), \\ \vec{r}(t + dt) &= \vec{r}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2} + \frac{dt}{2}\right) \approx \vec{r}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + \frac{dt}{2} \vec{v}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dt}{2}\right)^2 \vec{a}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + O(dt^3),\end{aligned}\tag{6.4}$$

where \vec{a} is the acceleration. Subtracting these two equations, we arrive at

$$\vec{r}(t + dt) = \vec{r}(t) + dt\vec{v}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + O(dt^3).\tag{6.5}$$

Doing the same thing for the velocity around time t :

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{v}\left(t - \frac{dt}{2}\right) &\approx \vec{v}(t) - \frac{dt}{2} \vec{a}(t) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dt}{2}\right)^2 \frac{d}{dt} \vec{a}(t) + O(dt^3), \\ \vec{v}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) &\approx \vec{v}(t) + \frac{dt}{2} \vec{a}(t) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dt}{2}\right)^2 \frac{d}{dt} \vec{a}(t) + O(dt^3).\end{aligned}\tag{6.6}$$

Analogously, subtracting these two equations, we arrive at

$$\vec{v}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) = \vec{v}\left(t - \frac{dt}{2}\right) + dt\vec{a}(t) + O(dt^3).\tag{6.7}$$

Note in Equation 6.5 and Equation 6.7 that the velocity and position of the particles predicted are not at the same time. Velocity is half a time step before or after, making the impression that

the position and velocity predictions jump over each other. Hence, the name of the algorithm is Leapfrog. The disadvantage of this method is that for the first time step, one needs to know the velocity at time $t - dt/2$. There are multiple ways of dealing with this. However, the one used in this work and one of the most popular ways is to do half a time step backward using the Eulers method.

There are many more integration schemes. For example, to name a few, the symplectic fourth-order Forest-Ruth [98], PEFRL [99], VEFRL [99], Suzuki [100], and Yoshida [101] algorithms, the fifth-order Gear algorithm [102][103], the third-order optimized Verlet [99], and the Runge-Kutta schemes [104]. These higher-order algorithms generally provide greater accuracy and stability than the leapfrog and Verlet methods and allow for larger time steps.

However, on the one hand, in the case of DEM simulations using the Hertz contact model, the time step must be smaller than the Hertz interaction time to ensure good results. This restriction limits the benefits of higher-order algorithms, as they often require more than one force computation per timestep. Force computations are the most expensive part of a DEM simulation. For this reason, using these algorithms is usually not worth it. Also, under this restriction, the time step is small enough for the Leapfrog and Verlet methods to be accurate and stable.

On the other hand, in simulations without a critical time step, such as in Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations, the use of higher-order algorithms can be beneficial. The increase in time step usually justifies the extra force computations.

6.2 Rotational Motion

Rotation integration algorithms solve the rigid body equations of motion to update particle orientation and angular velocity. The inertia tensor of a rigid body determines its dynamics. However, most rotating objects have non-constant inertia tensors measured in the lab reference frame. Fortunately, it is possible to find a reference frame fixed to the rigid body where the inertia tensor is diagonal. This reference frame is known as the principal axis reference frame, and it simplifies the equations while avoiding the expensive recalculation of the inertia tensor at every time step [105]. In this reference frame, the equations of motion for rigid bodies can be expressed as follows [106]:

$$\begin{aligned} I_x \dot{\omega}_x &= \tau_x + \omega_y \omega_z (I_y - I_z), \\ I_y \dot{\omega}_y &= \tau_y + \omega_z \omega_x (I_z - I_x), \\ I_z \dot{\omega}_z &= \tau_z + \omega_x \omega_y (I_x - I_y), \end{aligned} \tag{6.8}$$

where I_i are the components of the inertia tensor, ω_i the angular velocity, and τ_i the torque.

Using the angular velocity, we can calculate the new orientation of the rigid body. However, there are multiple ways to define orientation. One method is through Euler angles [106][70]. While Euler angles are relatively straightforward to use, they are susceptible to a phenomenon known as gimbal lock [107][108]. A gimbal lock occurs when two of the three rotational degrees of freedom become aligned, causing the system to lose one of them. A gimbal lock can cause the simulation

to crash or errors in the calculated orientation. Alternative, methods for defining orientation, such as quaternions [109] or Direction Cosine Matrix (DCM) [110], can be used to avoid gimbal locks. These methods offer advantages such as increased numerical stability and reduced computational cost, making them ideal for computational models. A quaternion is a four-dimensional vector consisting of a scalar and a three-element vector component. Quaternions are an extension of complex numbers and were invented by William Rowan Hamilton in 1843 [109].

In this work, we use a quaternion-based method to calculate orientation. Therefore, knowing the angular velocity in the particle reference frame, the quaternion's time derivative, [111, 112]

$$\dot{q} = \frac{dq}{dt} = \frac{1}{2}\omega q, \quad (6.9)$$

with $\omega = \{0, \omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z\}$ a pure imaginary quaternion representing the angular velocity $\vec{\omega} = \{\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z\}$ in the rotating body reference frame.

6.3 New Rotation Algorithm

Integrating rotations is challenging due to the non-linear nature of equations of motion, as explained in section 6.2. Despite this, many modern discrete element method (DEM) codes still use integration algorithms like Velocity Verlet or direct Euler, which are inefficient and cannot fully account for the complexities of rotational motion. Additionally, most of these algorithms require frequent quaternion normalization to maintain stability during simulations. The commonly used integration algorithms in popular DEM codes can be seen in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Integration algorithms for particle rotations and DEM software that use them.

Algorithm	DEM codes using it			
Direct Euler [90]	MFIX [91]	EDEM [92]	BlazeDEMGPU [93]	MUSEN [113]
Velocity Verlet [94]	LIGGGHTS [114]	GranOO [115]	EDEM [92]	MercuryDPM [41]
Fincham Leapfrog [116]	YADE [43]	Esys_Particle [117]	WooDEM [118]	
Buss [119]	PFC7 [120]			
Johnson et al. [121]	PFC7 [120]			
PFC4 algorithm [122, 123]	MercuryDPM [41]			

We have developed a new integration algorithm that overcomes the limitations of existing ones. This method addresses the issues of previous algorithms and improves upon their strengths. To begin the derivation, we must find an expression for $q(t + dt)$ by using Equation 6.9 and assuming that ω only depends on time. By separating the variables, we can elegantly derive the new algorithm.

$$\int_t^{t+dt} \frac{dq}{q} = \frac{1}{2} \int_t^{t+dt} \omega(t') dt', \quad (6.10)$$

To obtain

$$q(t + dt) = q(t) \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} \int_t^{t+dt} \omega(t') dt'\right). \quad (6.11)$$

Since $\omega(t')$ is unknown, we expand it in a Taylor series,

$$\omega(t') \approx \omega(a) + \dot{\omega}(a)(t' - a) + \frac{1}{2}\ddot{\omega}(a)(t' - a)^2 + \dots \quad (6.12)$$

If we take $a = t + \frac{dt}{2}$, to get a leapfrog approach, we end up with

$$q(t + dt) \approx q(t) \exp\left(\frac{dt}{2}\omega\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) + O(dt^3)\right), \text{ with } O(dt^3) \approx \frac{dt^3}{48}\ddot{\omega}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) \quad (6.13)$$

The exponential of a purely imaginary quaternion θu , where θ is a scalar and $u = \{0, u_x, u_y, u_z\}$, a unitary quaternion, is [112]

$$e^{\theta \hat{u}} = \cos \theta + \vec{u} \sin \theta \quad , \quad (6.14)$$

with $\vec{u} = \{u_x, u_y, u_z\}$ a unitary vector. The expression for $q(t + dt)$ becomes

$$q(t + dt) = q(t) \left(\cos \theta_1 + \frac{\vec{\omega}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right)}{|\vec{\omega}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right)|} \sin \theta_1 \right) \quad , \quad \theta_1 = \frac{dt}{2} \left| \vec{\omega}\left(t + \frac{dt}{2}\right) \right| \quad (6.15)$$

We can also find $q(t + dt)$ following a non-leapfrog approach if we take $a = t$ in Equation 6.12:

$$q(t + dt) \approx q(t) \exp\left(\frac{dt}{2}\omega(t) + \frac{dt^2}{4}\dot{\omega}(t) + O(dt^3)\right), \text{ with } O(dt^3) \approx \frac{dt^3}{12}\ddot{\omega}(t) \quad (6.16)$$

Then, using Equation 6.14

$$\begin{aligned} q(t + dt) &= q(t) \left(\cos \theta_2 + \frac{\vec{\omega}(t)}{|\vec{\omega}(t)|} \sin \theta_2 \right) \left(\cos \theta_3 + \frac{\ddot{\vec{\omega}}(t)}{|\ddot{\vec{\omega}}(t)|} \sin \theta_3 \right) \quad , \quad (6.17) \\ \theta_2 &= \frac{dt}{2} |\vec{\omega}(t)|, \quad \theta_3 = \frac{dt^2}{4} \left| \ddot{\vec{\omega}}(t) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

Our approach conserves the norm of the initial quaternion, thus eliminating the need for normalization. It shares similarities with the algorithm proposed by Buss (2000) [119], but we achieve a higher-order approximation.

For achieving optimal results, we need accurate calculations of the angular velocity. We can achieve this employing a Strong-Stability Preserving Runge-Kutta-3-like scheme (SSPRK3) [124]:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{K}_1 &= dt\vec{\omega}\left(\vec{\omega}, \vec{M}(t)\right) \quad , \\ \vec{K}_2 &= dt\vec{\omega}\left(\vec{\omega} + \vec{K}_1, \vec{M}(t)\right) \quad , \\ \vec{K}_3 &= dt\vec{\omega}\left(\vec{\omega} + \frac{1}{4}(\vec{K}_1 + \vec{K}_2), \vec{M}(t)\right) \quad , \\ \vec{\omega}(t + dt/2) &= \vec{\omega}(t - dt/2) + \frac{1}{6}\left(\vec{K}_1 + \vec{K}_2 + 4\vec{K}_3\right) \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (6.18)$$

where $\vec{M}(t)$ is the torque in the body principal axis reference frame and $\vec{\omega}$ is given by Euler's equations of motion (Equation 6.8).

We use SSPRK3 as it is highly stable, and involves fewer operations than Runge-Kutta-4 [104] or the iterative algorithm used by Omelyan [125], improving performance. The idea of using a Runge-Kutta-like algorithm comes from Johnson et al. [121] where they used Runge Kutta 4 with constant torque to calculate the quaternion. Then, we calculate the torque $\vec{M}(t)$ only once per time step (we approximate it as constant along the time step). When using a leapfrog scheme, $\vec{\omega}$ is updated before q . Therefore, it is necessary to compute the angular velocity at a half step back at the beginning of the simulation. This can be done using Equation 6.18 with $-dt/2$ instead of dt . In the non-leapfrog approach, $q(t)$ is updated before $\omega(t)$, and no starting step is required.

To compare the different algorithms we need a reference solution. Then, we found a solution for a special case of Equation 6.8. Assuming constant torque $\vec{M} = (M_x, 0, 0)$ where $M_x \neq 0$ and $\omega_x(t) \neq 0$ for all times and for a rigid body with $I_x \neq I_y = I_z$, like a cylinder, we have that Equation 6.8 reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} I_x \dot{\omega}_x &= M_x, \\ I_y \dot{\omega}_y &= \omega_z \omega_x (I_z - I_x), \\ I_z \dot{\omega}_z &= \omega_x \omega_y (I_x - I_y). \end{aligned} \tag{6.19}$$

The solution for ω_x is

$$\omega_x(t) = \omega_x(0) + \frac{M_x}{I_x} t. \tag{6.20}$$

The other two equations are harder to solve. To start, let's take the time derivatives on both sides of the equation for ω_y to get

$$\frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \ddot{\omega}_y = \dot{\omega}_z \omega_x + \omega_z \dot{\omega}_x. \tag{6.21}$$

Now, let us substitute $\dot{\omega}_z$ in the equation for ω_z to get

$$\frac{I_z}{I_x - I_y} \left(\frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{1}{\omega_x} \ddot{\omega}_y - \frac{\dot{\omega}_x}{\omega_x} \omega_z \right) = \omega_x \omega_y. \tag{6.22}$$

To continue, we need to assume that ω_x is never zero. From Equation 6.19 we can substitute ω_z to get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{I_z}{I_x - I_y} \left(\frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{1}{\omega_x} \ddot{\omega}_y - \frac{\dot{\omega}_x}{\omega_x} \frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{1}{\omega_x} \dot{\omega}_y \right) &= \omega_x \omega_y, \\ A \left(\ddot{\omega}_y - \frac{\dot{\omega}_x}{\omega_x} \dot{\omega}_y \right) &= \omega_x^2 \omega_y, \quad \text{with } A = \frac{I_z I_y}{(I_x - I_y)(I_z - I_x)}. \end{aligned} \tag{6.23}$$

Regardless if $I_x < I_y$ or $I_x > I_y$, $A < 0$. Defining $B = A^{-1}$, the equation reduces to

$$\ddot{\omega}_y - \frac{\dot{\omega}_x}{\omega_x} \dot{\omega}_y = B \omega_x^2 \omega_y. \tag{6.24}$$

Now, replacing ω_x with Equation 6.20 and performing the change of variable $t^* = \omega_x(0) + \frac{M_x}{I_x}t$. The equation becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
t^* &= \omega_x(0) + \frac{M_x}{I_x}t, \\
dt^* &= \frac{M_x}{I_x}dt, \\
\frac{d\omega_y}{dt} &= \frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*} \frac{dt^*}{dt} = \frac{M_x}{I_x} \frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*}, \\
\frac{d^2\omega_y}{dt^2} &= \frac{M_x}{I_x} \frac{d}{dt^*} \frac{dt^*}{dt} \frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*} = \left(\frac{M_x}{I_x}\right)^2 \frac{d^2\omega_y}{dt^{*2}}, \\
\left(\frac{M_x}{I_x}\right)^2 \frac{d^2\omega_y}{dt^{*2}} - \frac{M_x}{I_x} \frac{\dot{\omega}_x}{\omega_x} \frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*} &= B\omega_x^2\omega_y.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.25}$$

Using Equation 6.20, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\frac{M_x}{I_x}\right)^2 \frac{d^2\omega_y}{dt^{*2}} - \left(\frac{M_x}{I_x}\right)^2 \frac{1}{t^*} \frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*} &= B\omega_x^2\omega_y, \\
\ddot{\omega}_y - \frac{1}{t^*}\dot{\omega}_y &= Ct^{*2}\omega_y.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.26}$$

Note that $C < 0$. To solve the new equation, let us perform another change of variable,

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= t^{*2}, \\
dx &= 2t^* dt^*, \\
\frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*} &= \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} \frac{dx}{dt^*} = 2t^* \frac{d\omega_y}{dx}, \\
\frac{d^2\omega_y}{dt^{*2}} &= \frac{d}{dt^*} \left(2t^* \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} \right) = 2 \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} + 2t^* \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dx}{dt^*} \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} = 2 \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} + 4x \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d\omega_y}{dx}.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.27}$$

Replacing, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
2 \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} + 4x \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} - \frac{1}{t^*} 2t^* \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} &= Ct^{*2}\omega_y, \\
4x \frac{d^2\omega_y}{dx^2} &= Cx\omega_y, \\
\frac{d^2\omega_y}{dx^2} &= \frac{C}{4}\omega_y = D\omega_y.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.28}$$

Now, Proposing a solution of the kind $\omega_y = e^{\lambda x}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda^2 e^{\lambda x} &= D e^{\lambda x}, \\
\lambda^2 &= D, \\
\lambda &= \pm\sqrt{D}.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.29}$$

We know that $D < 0$. Then, λ is a complex number. Then, the solution is

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_y(x) &= C_1 e^{i\eta x} + C_2 e^{-i\eta x}. \\ \eta &= \sqrt{|D|}.\end{aligned}\tag{6.30}$$

Using Euler's identity $e^{i\beta} = \cos \beta + i \sin \beta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_y(x) &= C_1(\cos(\eta x) + i \sin(\eta x)) + C_2(\cos(\eta x) - i \sin(\eta x)), \\ \omega_y(x) &= K_1 \cos(\eta x) + K_2 \sin(\eta x).\end{aligned}\tag{6.31}$$

Next, we then can use [Equation 6.19](#) to solve for ω_z as

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_z(t) &= \frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{1}{\omega_x} \dot{\omega}_y = \frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{1}{t^*} \frac{M_x}{I_x} \frac{d\omega_y}{dt^*} = \frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{1}{t^*} \frac{M_x}{I_x} 2t^* \frac{d\omega_y}{dx}, \\ \omega_z(x) &= 2 \frac{I_y}{I_z - I_x} \frac{M_x}{I_x} \frac{d\omega_y}{dx} = E \frac{d\omega_y}{dx}, \\ \omega_z(x) &= E\eta (K_2 \cos(\eta x) - K_1 \sin(\eta x)).\end{aligned}\tag{6.32}$$

To find out what K_1 and K_2 are, we need to evaluate the initial conditions.

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_y(t=0) &= K_1 \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2) + K_2 \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2). \\ \omega_z(t=0) &= E\eta (K_2 \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2) - K_1 \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)).\end{aligned}\tag{6.33}$$

The solution for this system of equations is

$$\begin{aligned}K_1 &= \frac{E\eta\omega_y(0) \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2) - \omega_z(0) \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)}{E\eta \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)^2 + E\eta \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)^2} = \frac{E\eta\omega_y(0) \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2) - \omega_z(0) \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)}{E\eta}, \\ K_2 &= \frac{E\eta\omega_y(0) \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2) + \omega_z(0) \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)}{E\eta \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)^2 + E\eta \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)^2} = \frac{E\eta\omega_y(0) \sin(\eta\omega_x(0)^2) + \omega_z(0) \cos(\eta\omega_x(0)^2)}{E\eta}.\end{aligned}\tag{6.34}$$

Then, the solution of [Equation 6.8](#) is

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_x(t) &= \sqrt{x} = \omega_x(0) + \frac{M_x}{I_x} t, \\ \omega_y(x) &= K_1 \cos(\eta x) + K_2 \sin(\eta x), \\ \omega_z(x) &= \omega_z(x) = E\eta (K_2 \cos(\eta x) - K_1 \sin(\eta x)),\end{aligned}\tag{6.35}$$

with $\vec{\omega}(0)$ the initial angular velocity and

$$\begin{aligned}\eta &= \frac{I_x}{2M_x} \sqrt{\frac{|(I_x - I_y)(I_z - I_x)|}{I_y I_z}}, & E &= \frac{2I_y M_x}{I_x(I_z - I_x)}, \\ K_1 &= \omega_y(0) \cos(\eta \omega_x(0)^2) - \frac{1}{E\eta} \omega_z(0) \sin(\eta \omega_x(0)^2), \\ K_2 &= \omega_y(0) \sin(\eta \omega_x(0)^2) + \frac{1}{E\eta} \omega_z(0) \cos(\eta \omega_x(0)^2).\end{aligned}\tag{6.36}$$

We have solved the angular velocity analytically and will refer to it as $\vec{\omega}'$. To calculate the body orientation, we use numerical integration of [Equation 6.9](#) with the highly accurate *DifferentialEquations.jl* package [126]. The resulting numerical solution is referred to as q' .

The analytic solution corresponds to a cylinder, that rotates while suspended in space and subject to a constant torque. To compare the different integration algorithms, we consider a cylinder with radius 5.00 cm, height 15.00 cm, and density 7750 kg/m³. Then, the inertia tensor in the principal axis frame is $\vec{I} = \{0.0114, 0.0228, 0.0228\}$ kg m², initial angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_0 = \{0.300, -0.900, 0.600\}$ rad/s, initial orientation $q_0 = \{1, 0, 0, 0\}$, a constant torque of $M_x = 0.500$ N m. In [Figure 6.1](#), the analytical solution uses these parameters.

Figure 6.1: Plot of the analytical solution for the angular velocity ([Equation 6.35](#)) at the right and at the left plot of the numerical solution of [Equation 6.9](#) using the analytically derived angular velocity and the *DifferentialEquations.jl* package [126].

We can compare the accuracy and stability of the different integration algorithms. In [Figure 6.2](#) the error of each algorithm is plotted against the time step on a logarithmic scale. The error metric used is the norm of the difference between the reference solutions ($\vec{\omega}'$ and q') and the predictions generated by each algorithm divided by the norm of the reference.

Figure 6.2: Error for the predicted quaternion q (left) and angular velocity ω (right) after 1.0 s of simulation time plotted against the time step dt for various integration algorithms when calculating the rotational motion of the rotating body described by Equation 6.35. Our proposed algorithm (red line).

As accuracy is not everything, we can also evaluate the stability of each integration algorithm. To test the stability we plot the error against simulation time in Figure 6.3, using a fixed time step of $dt = 10^{-5}$ s.

Figure 6.3: Error against time t for the quaternion q (left) and the angular velocity ω (right) when using the same time step ($dt = 10^{-5}$ s) for various integration algorithms when calculating the rotational motion of the rotating body described by Equation 6.35. The errors are computed as in Figure 6.2. Our proposed algorithm (red line).

We carried out simulations to test the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm in real-world situations. These simulations were designed to reflect more practical conditions and assess the algorithm’s accuracy, stability, and energy conservation in complex dynamic systems. Our focus was on evaluating its ability to maintain stability and energy conservation in a dynamic environment by simulating the behavior of non-spherical particles in a frictionless and damping-free box. This allowed us to remove dissipative forces and focus on the algorithm’s ability to conserve energy. In the simulation, we used nonspherical particles (chess pieces) with dimensions following the recommendations of FIDE (e.g., King: 9.5 cm, Queen: 8.5 cm, Bishop: 7 cm, Knight: 6 cm, Rook: 5.5 cm, Pawn: 5 cm). The density of the particles was 3200 kg/m^3 , with a Young’s modulus of 60 GPa and a Poisson ratio of 0.25. We employed the Hertz-Mindlin contact model explained in [chapter 7](#). The simulations were carried out in YADE [43]. We randomly assigned initial positions to the objects, ensuring that there were no overlaps between them. Each object was given an initial velocity of 1.0 m/s in a randomly chosen direction, and the initial angular velocity was set to π rad/s in another randomly chosen direction. A snapshot of the simulated system can be seen in [Figure 6.4](#).

Figure 6.4: A set of chess pieces bouncing in a box.

In [Figure 6.5](#) we can see the ability of the algorithm to conserve energy in the simulation in [Figure 6.4](#).

Our analysis primarily focused on comparing the performance of our proposed algorithm using the LeapFrog version, which proved to be more efficient. However, we also developed a non-LeapFrog version of the algorithm that exhibited comparable efficiency. We conducted the same benchmarks for the non-LeapFrog algorithm as those presented in [Figure 6.2](#) and [Figure 6.3](#). The results are in [Figure 6.6](#) and [Figure 6.7](#). In addition, we incorporated the use of the Omelyan angular velocity calculation in our algorithm to provide a comparison against this alternative approach, which is highly beneficial for MD simulations as Omelyan provides a modified version of

Figure 6.5: Average % energy change through the simulation. $100|E_0 - E_f|/E_0$. This was sampled 250 times over the whole simulation, and the reported quantity in the graph is the average of all the samples.

its algorithm with a thermostat [127].

Figure 6.6: Error for the predicted quaternion q (left) and angular velocity ω (right) after 1.0 s of simulation time plotted against the time step dt for our proposed algorithms

Figure 6.7: Error against time t for the quaternion q (left) and the angular velocity ω (right) when using the same time step ($dt = 10^{-5}$ s) for our proposed algorithms.

In summary, we tested various rotation integration algorithms using a realistic simulation setup and an analytical solution. This helped us evaluate the performance of each algorithm, and we found that our proposed algorithm was accurate, stable, and efficient in conserving energy. Our results confirmed the algorithm's effectiveness in practical scenarios and outperformed all other algorithms we compared it with while maintaining a similar computational cost. Though our algorithm is slower than the Direct Euler method for a single time step (about 50 %), its improved stability allows larger time steps, resulting in faster simulations. We summarized the speedup achieved compared to the Direct Euler method in [Table 6.2](#) for reaching a target error within 1.0 seconds of simulation time. To determine the time step required to achieve the target error, we used the data from [Figure 6.2](#) and the bracketing algorithm from `Roots.jl` [128]. Finally, we measured the total simulation time using `BenchmarkTools.jl` package [129].

Table 6.2: Execution time speedup achieved for the various integration algorithms with respect to Direct Euler method when computing the rotational motion of the body described by Equation 6.35. The time steps dt for each case (shown after the /) are chosen to achieve the same combined target error $(|q - q'|/|q'| + |\omega - \omega'|/|\omega'|)/2$ after 1.0 s of simulation time. Our proposed algorithm is the faster one for all cases in the table.

Speedup / Time step Algorithm	Target Error			
	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	10^{-3}	10^{-2}
del Valle et al. LeapFrog	730x / 3.41e-03	x105 / 9.44e-03	13.1x / 2.48e-02	2.26x / 6.36e-02
Omelyan	143x / 2.94e-04	37.9x / 9.29e-04	8.08x / 2.94e-03	1.98x / 9.39e-03
Buss	14.4x / 3.23e-05	13.5x / 3.25e-04	7.50x / 3.54e-03	2.23x / 6.48e-02
Velocity Verlet	6.01x / 8.77e-06	5.91x / 8.82e-05	4.17x / 8.39e-04	1.19x / 4.17e-03
Fincham	2.27x / 4.55e-06	2.35x / 4.52e-05	2.16x / 4.58e-04	1.56x / 4.99e-03
Direct Euler	1x / 1.44e-06	1x / 1.44e-05	1x / 1.45e-04	1x / 1.59e-03
Johnson et al.	0.469x / 1.79e-06	0.471x / 1.79e-05	0.493x / 1.79e-04	0.613x / 1.79e-03
MercuryDMP	0.103x / 2.60e-07	0.109x / 2.60e-06	0.114x / 2.61e-05	0.184x / 2.66e-04

The New DEM Force Model

Analyzing complex systems through traditional analytical methods can be difficult. However, computer simulations can be a powerful tool for replicating interactions and reproducing the expected behaviors of complex systems. This chapter delves into the DEM force model used in this work, which is foundational for simulating granular material dynamics. Furthermore, we will capitalize on the theory of the previous chapters to propose our new force model.

7.1 Contact forces

The purpose of the following section is to lay the foundation for understanding the Hertz-Mindlin force model [81], for it is the model that we will be using to describe the contact between particles.

7.1.1 Normal Forces

We will consider two distinct normal forces. Firstly, the Hertz contact force, as elaborated in [section 3.2](#). This force arises due to the elastic deformation experienced by particles upon contact and depends on various factors, including particle shape, size, and material properties. The second normal force at play is the plastic force, which accounts for the energy dissipation during particle contact. This force represents the irreversibility of interactions and is essential for capturing realistic behaviors in our simulations. To quantify the energy lost during collisions, we rely on the restitution coefficient introduced in [section 3.3](#). Consider the normal unitary vector that points in the direction of the interaction:

$$\hat{n} = \frac{\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|}. \quad (7.1)$$

Then, the normal force experienced by the particles is given by

$$\vec{F}_n = \max\left(0, \frac{4}{3}E^*\sqrt{R^*}h^{3/2} - \vec{F}_{damp} \cdot \hat{n}\right) \cdot \hat{n}, \quad (7.2)$$

where E^* , R^* are defined in [section 3.2](#) and h is the penetration depth. As a reminder:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{E^*} &= \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i} + \frac{1 - \nu_j^2}{E_j}. \\ \frac{1}{R^*} &= \frac{1}{R_i} + \frac{1}{R_j}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.3}$$

Note that the resulting force can never be attractive. This would be nonphysical behavior. For the damping force, we have two options. One assumes that the restitution coefficient is constant, and the other one that it depends on the impact velocity. Experiments have shown that the restitution coefficient depends on the impact velocity [[130](#)]. However, this makes the model much more complicated. Let us begin with the model where the restitution coefficient is constant. As proposed by [[81](#)], the force is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{F}_{damp} &= 2\gamma\sqrt{m^*k_n}\vec{v}_{ij}, \\ k_n &= 2E^*\sqrt{R^*h}, \\ \frac{1}{m^*} &= \frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{m_j},\end{aligned}\tag{7.4}$$

where m^* is the reduced mass and \vec{v}_{ij} is the relative impact velocity. γ is a fitting parameter that ensures that the damping coefficient is kept constant and is given by [[131](#)]

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha &= e_n(h_1 + e_n(h_2 + e_n(h_3 + e_n(h_4 + e_n(h_5 + e_n(h_6 + e_n(h_7 + e_n(h_8 + e_n(h_9 + e_n h_{10})))))))))). \\ \gamma &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{1 - (1 + e_n)^2 e^\alpha} - 1}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.5}$$

With

$$\begin{aligned}h_1 &= -6.918798, \\ h_2 &= -16.41105, \\ h_3 &= 146.8049, \\ h_4 &= -796.4559, \\ h_5 &= 2928.711, \\ h_6 &= -7206.864, \\ h_7 &= 11494.29, \\ h_8 &= -11342.18, \\ h_9 &= 6276.757, \\ h_{10} &= -1489.915.\end{aligned}\tag{7.6}$$

The second model was motivated by the Kuwabara Kono force model [132] and rigorously derived in [133, 134]. The model reads

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{F}_{damp} &= \frac{3}{2}A\rho\sqrt{h}\vec{v}_{ij}. \\ \rho &= \frac{4}{3}E^*\sqrt{R^*}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.7}$$

The problem with this model is that A is unknown. Then, [82] proposed a way of calculating it. Using Padé approximants, we can calculate the restitution coefficient as a function of impact velocity

$$\begin{aligned}e_n(v^*) &= \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m a_i v_*^i}{\sum_{i=0}^n b_i v_*^i}. \\ v_* &= \beta^{1/2} v^{1/10}. \\ \beta &= \frac{3}{2}A \left(\frac{\rho}{m^*}\right)^{2/5}. \\ a_i &= \{1.0, 1.07232, 0.574198, 0.141552\}. \\ b_i &= \{1.0, 1.07232, 1.72765, 1.37842, 1.19449, 0.467273, 0.235585\}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.8}$$

To determine the restitution coefficient of the particle at a specific impact velocity, we utilize a root-finding algorithm to calculate the velocity threshold v_* . This threshold allows us to achieve the desired restitution coefficient. Once v_* is obtained, we use with the predetermined impact velocity to calculate the value of A .

7.1.2 Tangent Forces

Tangent forces represent friction between particles. Is given by

$$\vec{F}_t = \begin{cases} (k_t \Delta x + \vec{F}_{damp} \cdot \hat{t})\hat{t} & \text{if } |\vec{F}_t| < \mu_s F_n \\ \mu_k F_n \hat{t} & \text{In other case} \end{cases}\tag{7.9}$$

where μ_s is the static friction coefficient, μ_k is the slipping friction coefficient (most codes assume they are equal), Δx is the distance traveled by the contact and needs to be updated each time step where the contact is present. \hat{t} is the unitary tangent vector to the contact. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta x_n &= \Delta x_{n-1} + dt \vec{v}_{ij} \cdot \hat{t}. \\ k_t &= 8G^* \sqrt{R^* h}. \\ \hat{t} &= \frac{\vec{v}_{ij} - \vec{v}_{ij} \cdot \hat{n}}{|\vec{v}_{ij} - \vec{v}_{ij} \cdot \hat{n}|}. \\ \frac{1}{G^*} &= \frac{2 - \nu_i}{G_i} + \frac{2 - \nu_j}{G_j}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.10}$$

7.2 Beam Forces

In this section, we will discuss the new force model proposed in this work. Specifically, we will explore how we can use the beam forces described in [section 5.3](#) and [section 5.4](#) to bond two spheres together. To accomplish this, we need to create stiffness and damping matrices for each beam connection. However, performing these matrix multiplications every time step can be costly. Fortunately, we have found a way to improve performance. We will still use matrix notation to explain the force model because it is simpler to understand, and we will present the performance-improved version at the end. Having the matrices, we can calculate the force and torque acting on each sphere with

$$FT = D\dot{U} + KU. \quad (7.11)$$

The components of FT represent the forces and torques acting on two particles. The first three components indicate the force acting on the first particle, while the next three represent the torque acting on the first particle. The following three components indicate the force acting on the second particle, and the last three represent the torque acting on the second particle. Note that the force is equally strong but opposite in direction for both particles, but the torques are not. The forces and torques must be transformed from the beam reference frame to the lab or particle frame afterward. The components in U and \dot{U} work similarly. The first components in U indicate the relative spatial and angular translation of the first particles, and the last ones indicate the spatial and angular displacements of the second particle. In \dot{U} , they correspond to the relative velocity and angular velocity, also in the beam reference frame. The formulation in [section 5.3](#) and [section 5.4](#) assumes that the reference frame is in the center of the beam. Therefore, the displacement in one direction of the first particle is the same but opposite for the other particle. Remember that the beam is always aligned with the x-axis in its reference frames.

As shown in [Figure 7.1](#), the beam's measurements can be adjusted to meet specific requirements. The beam is not restricted to connecting the centers of the two spheres only. Moreover, the distance between the spheres and the beam's thickness is arbitrary. This force model was implemented in YADE [\[43\]](#) using a circular cross-section. However, by modifying the second moments of area, section modulus, and cross-sectional area values, is possible to simulate beams with different cross-section shapes. It is important to note that when either x_i or x_j is non-zero, the additional torque resulting from the forces at the beam ends needs to be considered. The model also handles the case where the spheres overlap. Is up to the user to decide if two bounded spheres can have a Hertz contact or not.

Figure 7.1: Schematic representation of the dimensions of the beam connecting two spheres. The spheres can overlap is desired.

To calculate the values of U and \dot{U} , it is necessary to determine the current reference frame of the beam. Additionally, it is important to calculate the relative twisting between the two ends of the beam. This requires storing the initial orientation of the beam q_{0b} (the quaternion that aligns the beam with the x-axis). It is also necessary to store the initial quaternions of the spheres at each end. By utilizing this information, we calculate the orientation of the beam as seen from the perspective of each sphere:

$$\begin{aligned} q_{bi} &= q_i \cdot q_{0i}^{-1} \cdot q_{0b} \\ q_{bj} &= q_j \cdot q_{0j}^{-1} \cdot q_{0b} \end{aligned} \quad (7.12)$$

We can choose either of them for the ongoing calculations, but for better numerical stability we should take the average of the two to get

$$q_b = \text{slerp}(0.5, q_{bi}, q_{bj}). \quad (7.13)$$

Slerp is the operation used to average quaternions. Now that we have the beam orientation, we can calculate the spatial displacement as

$$\Delta \vec{r} = \frac{1}{2} (R^{-1} \cdot (\vec{r}_j - \vec{r}_i) - (L + x_i + x_j)\hat{x}). \quad (7.14)$$

Where R is the rotation matrix that corresponds to q_b , x_i the distance from the center of the sphere i to its closest beam end, x_j the distance from the center of the sphere j to its closest beam end, and L the beam length. The factor $\frac{1}{2}$ is due to the fact that the reference frame is in the center of the beam. The angle displacement can be calculated easily by taking advantage of the angle axis

representation of quaternions as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{bending} &= \text{Angle_Axis}(q_{bi}^{-1} \cdot q_{bj}). \\ \Delta\vec{\theta} &= \frac{1}{2}\text{bending.angle} \cdot \text{bending.axis}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.15)$$

The relative velocity and angular velocity can be calculated with

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\vec{r} &= \frac{1}{2}R^{-1}(\vec{v}_j - \vec{v}_i). \\ \Delta\vec{\theta} &= \frac{1}{2}R^{-1}(\vec{\theta}_j - \vec{\theta}_i). \end{aligned} \quad (7.16)$$

Finally, using the force on each beam, we can use the Mohr Culomb failure criteria explained in [section 4.3](#) with the principal stresses explained in [section 5.2](#) to asses if the beam should break or not.

To avoid performing the matrix multiplication each timestep, we can solve the matrix multiplication analytically and see what the forces and torque should be. This gives us that the elastic force and torques are

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F} &= \left(\frac{2AE\Delta r_x}{L}, \frac{24EI_z\Delta r_y}{L^3}, \frac{24EI_y\Delta r_z}{L^3} \right). \\ \vec{M}_i &= \left(\frac{2GJ\Delta\theta_x}{L}, \frac{2EI_y\Delta\theta_y}{L} - \frac{12EI_y\Delta r_z}{L^2}, \frac{2EI_z\Delta\theta_z}{L} + \frac{12EI_z\Delta r_y}{L^2} \right). \\ \vec{M}_j &= \left(-\frac{2GJ\Delta\theta_x}{L}, -\frac{2EI_y\Delta\theta_y}{L} - \frac{12EI_y\Delta r_z}{L^2}, -\frac{2EI_z\Delta\theta_z}{L} + \frac{12EI_z\Delta r_y}{L^2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (7.17)$$

The damping force and torques are

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F} &= \left(\frac{1}{6}ALa_0\Delta\dot{r}_x\rho + \frac{2AEa_1\Delta\dot{r}_x}{L}, \frac{1}{12}AL^2a_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_z\rho + \frac{17}{70}ALa_0\Delta\dot{r}_y\rho + \frac{24EI_za_1\Delta\dot{r}_y}{L^3}, \right. \\ &\quad \left. -\frac{1}{12}AL^2a_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_y\rho + \frac{17}{70}ALa_0\Delta\dot{r}_z\rho + \frac{24EI_ya_1\Delta\dot{r}_z}{L^3} \right). \\ \vec{M}_i &= \left(\frac{1}{6}IxLa_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_x\rho + \frac{2GJa_1\Delta\dot{\theta}_x}{L}, \frac{1}{60}AL^3a_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_y\rho - \frac{3}{140}AL^2a_0\Delta\dot{r}_z\rho + \frac{2EI_ya_1\Delta\dot{\theta}_y}{L} - \frac{12EI_ya_1\Delta\dot{r}_z}{L^2}, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{1}{60}AL^3a_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_z\rho + \frac{3}{140}AL^2a_0\Delta\dot{r}_y\rho + \frac{2EI_za_1\Delta\dot{\theta}_z}{L} + \frac{12EI_za_1\Delta\dot{r}_y}{L^2} \right). \\ \vec{M}_j &= \left(-\frac{1}{6}IxLa_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_x\rho - \frac{2GJa_1\Delta\dot{\theta}_x}{L}, -\frac{1}{60}AL^3a_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_y\rho - \frac{3}{140}AL^2a_0\Delta\dot{r}_z\rho - \frac{2EI_ya_1\Delta\dot{\theta}_y}{L} - \frac{12EI_ya_1\Delta\dot{r}_z}{L^2}, \right. \\ &\quad \left. -\frac{1}{60}AL^3a_0\Delta\dot{\theta}_z\rho + \frac{3}{140}AL^2a_0\Delta\dot{r}_y\rho - \frac{2EI_za_1\Delta\dot{\theta}_z}{L} + \frac{12EI_za_1\Delta\dot{r}_y}{L^2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (7.18)$$

This force model was implemented in YADE [\[43\]](#) as part of this work.

Model Validation & Applications

This chapter will focus on the test cases used to evaluate the accuracy and validity of the force model introduced in [chapter 7](#). Additionally, we will explore some of the possible applications that can benefit from this force model aside from the main focus of this work which is the simulation of adobe structures.

8.1 Beams Benchmarks

This section presents a series of benchmarks to evaluate the accuracy of the force model for beam-like forces. The tests involve comparing the model with the forces experienced by a beam and using the analytical expression for beam deformation from [chapter 5](#). The values of l_0 , x_i , and x_j are zero, and the radius of the beam cross-section is equal to the smallest among the two spheres, following the notation in [Figure 7.1](#). The test involves using a chain of 30 spheres with mass $m = 1$, radius $r = 1$, and appropriate boundary conditions. The comparison is made by analyzing the positions of the sphere centers once the beam reaches a steady state due to Rayleigh damping ([section 5.4](#)). The analytical solution based on the Euler-Bernoulli beam approximation ([section 5.1](#)) is used as a reference. The beams have Young's modulus of $E = 10^6$ and a Poisson ratio of $\nu = 0.3$. Gravity is $g = -10$.

The first test focuses on a cantilever beam. The displacement of the beam is calculated using [Equation 5.6](#), and its solution is given by [Equation 5.7](#). A comparison between the equation and the simulation data is depicted in [Figure 8.1](#), showcasing the plot of the displacement.

Figure 8.1: Comparison of the displacement of a cantilever beam obtained from simulation data and the analytical solution. The plot shows the variation in displacement along the beam length, with the solid line representing the analytical solution and the marks representing the simulation data.

The second test examines a fixed simply supported beam, where both ends are fixed and not allowed to rotate. The analytical solution for this case is expressed as:

$$\eta(x) = \frac{mg}{L} \frac{x^2}{24EI} (L - x)^2, \quad (8.1)$$

where m is the mass of the beam. [Figure 8.2](#) presents a plot comparing the simulation data with the analytical solution.

Figure 8.2: Comparison of the displacement of a fixed simply supported beam obtained from simulation data and the analytical solution. The plot shows the variation in displacement along the beam length, with the solid line representing the analytical solution and the marks representing the simulation data.

8.2 Deformable Bodies

In this section, we demonstrate the model's capability to depict deformable elastic bodies. We use a cube made of spheres as an example, which showcases dynamic interactions with the floor. As the cube comes in contact with the ground, it undergoes deformation and compression, but later regains its original shape upon leaving the floor. [Figure 8.3](#) displays the progressive snapshots of the cube's interaction with the floor. The images show the cube's deformation and compression as it makes contact with the floor and its subsequent recovery as it separates from the ground.

Figure 8.3: The images show an elastic cube that changes shape when it comes into contact with the floor. It gets squished and compressed to fit the surface but returns to its original form when no longer in contact.

In addition, we illustrate how the body can break. Figure 8.4 shows another set of snapshots, similar to the previous ones, but this time the cube is allowed to break when it hits the floor. This demonstrates the force model’s ability to handle breakage in dynamic situations.

Figure 8.4: The images show an elastic cube that shatters when it comes into contact with the floor.

With these capabilities, this model may be able to simulate deformable elastic bodies like hydrogels and more.

8.3 Tunable Elasticity Material

One interesting application of this model is to simulate materials with adjustable elasticity. A study published in Scientific Reports [47] characterized a material made of glass beads connected by hardened glue. Surprisingly, this material exhibited behavior that was between that of wet granular material and cemented/sintered material. By adjusting Young’s modulus of the glue, the stiffness of the material changed by several orders of magnitude. Additionally, the material showed linear elasticity instead of the typical Hertzian force profile, indicating that the glue bridges drove its behavior. This material, which features spheres bonded by elastic bonds, is similar to the model proposed in this work. To test the model, we replicated the experimental results obtained by the authors.

In their experiment, Hemmerle et al. [47] performed an unconfined uniaxial compression test on a cylindrical sample made of the material of interest. The sample had dimensions of 4.9 mm in height and 4.65 mm in diameter. The material consisted of glass beads with a diameter of 210 μm and a polydispersity of 5%. The glass beads had Young’s modulus of 65 GPa, a Poisson’s ratio of 0.2, and a density of 2495 kg/m^3 . The friction coefficient between glass beads was measured to be $\mu_k = 0.4$. In the experiment, they used about 9800 beads. In the results presented here, we used about 3000 spheres for the simulations.

The Young’s modulus of the beams was assumed to be equal to the Young’s modulus of the glue. However, to account for measurement uncertainties, a normal distribution was employed with the reported measurement as the mean and a standard deviation of 5% of the mean. As the glue is incompressible, the Poisson’s ratio is 0.5.

Figure 8.5: Images of the glass beads bounded by hardened glue and the experimental set up in [47]. Taken from the cited paper.

The length of the beams, denoted by L , is determined by the equation:

$$L = l_0 + 2R \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{r^2}{R^2}} \right), \quad (8.2)$$

where l_0 follows the notation in Figure 7.1 and is equal to $5 \mu\text{m}$ except for the sample with the higher Young modulus where $l_0 = 2 \mu\text{m}$. R represents the radius of the smaller sphere in the connection, while $\frac{r^2}{R^2}$ denotes the ratio between the radius of the beam and the radius of the sphere. According to the experimental results, this ratio ranges from 0.03 to 1.0, depending on the glue content in the connection. Thus, to simulate the varying cross-section areas of the glue bridges observed in the paper, a random value within this range is generated for each beam to assign its radius. Then, knowing the radius of the spheres, the length of the beam, and the value of l_0 , we calculated x_i and x_j to carry out the calculations. In this simulation we allow two connected spheres to experience Hertz forces.

Additionally, the tensile strength of the glue reported by the manufacturer is 6.4 MPa [135], and an internal friction angle of $\pi/4$ was used for the Mohr-Coulomb failure criteria (see chapter 4). It is important to mention that the Young modulus of the glue can be controlled by adjusting the amount of curing agent. As a result, the cohesion value used for the failure criteria calculation may not be entirely precise.

Figure 8.6 displays the results of the uniaxial compression tests conducted. The plot showcases the simulated data obtained using the proposed model alongside the experimental measurements for easy comparison. The agreement between the simulated and experimental results demonstrates the ability of the model to capture the behavior of the material.

Figure 8.6: Comparison of simulated and experimental results for uniaxial compression tests of a cylinder of glass beads bounded with hard glue. E_p denotes the Young modulus of the glue bridges.

Despite certain approximations made in the simulation parameters, such as the cohesion and angle of internal friction in the failure criteria, as well as the range of beam thicknesses, all other parameters used in the simulation were identical to those used in the experiment. This minimal calibration requirement shows that the model can accurately replicate the material’s behavior and yield similar results as measured in the experiment. Table 8.1 shows the Young modulus of the material obtained in the simulation and in the experiment.

Table 8.1: Comparison of Young’s modulus values obtained from the experiment and simulation using various glue bridges, with E_p representing Young’s modulus of the glue bridges.

E_p MPa	Experiment	Simulation
1.51	4.91 ± 0.05	5.4 ± 0.1
0.64	3.44 ± 0.04	3.3 ± 0.1
0.09	1.56 ± 0.02	1.2 ± 0.1
0.02	0.32 ± 0.004	0.26 ± 0.01

It is worth noting that the differences in the results are due to the absence of calibration for the unknown braking parameters and the use of a smaller system compared to the one used in the real experiment. Moreover, the fracture behavior was not accurately recorded, as seen in Figure 8.6, probably because of the same reason. Unfortunately, we did not have enough time to investigate deeply this material.

Notwithstanding these limitations, the remarkable similarity observed in the results highlights the potential of this model to represent this system. With the missing calibration, it could become a highly accurate tool for analyzing and understanding these types of material. It is important to

point out that the authors of the experiment have done further research on these materials and have developed a numerical model of their own [136, 137, 138].

Simulations of Adobe Masonry Bricks

This chapter focuses on the simulation of adobe masonry using the force model introduced in [chapter 7](#). The objective is to accurately simulate adobe bricks, starting with a calibration test involving a three-point flexural simulation of a single brick. The experimental data was provided by Prof. Caori Takeuchi and her research group and the measurements were performed by Jhonatan Augusto Forero Pabón [62, 61] at the Department of Civil and Agricultural Engineering at the National University of Colombia, Bogotá.

9.1 One Adobe Brick

In this section, we conduct a 3-point flexural test simulation on an adobe brick. By comparing the simulation results with experimental data, we aim to calibrate our model and ensure its accuracy in depicting the material's behavior. To perform the 3-point flexural test, we subject the adobe brick to controlled loading conditions and observe its response. The results of the simulations were compared with the experimental data provided by Prof. Caori Takeuchi and her research group and the measurements were performed by Jhonatan Augusto Forero Pabón [62, 61] at the Department of Civil and Agricultural Engineering at the National University of Colombia, Bogotá.

First and foremost, the tests consist of loading a $350 \times 100 \times 170$ mm brick supported by two steel cylinders. The radii of the supporting cylinders are 1.5 cm. The cylinders were chosen to reproduce the experimental setup, but also - and more relevantly - they allow the ends of the brick to rotate while it is being pressed. This effectively sets the boundary conditions. To load the brick, we used a steel rod with a squared cross-section, with dimensions $10 \times 204 \times 10$ mm. The supporting cylinders have similar dimensions. In [Figure 9.1](#), a diagram of the geometry used in the test can be seen. It is worth mentioning that we used two different approaches for the simulations. The first one builds a brick out of spheres joined by beams, and the second one uses Voronoï polyhedra represented as multi-spheres, and the spheres of any two intersecting polyhedra with a common face are connected with beams.

Figure 9.1: Schematic representation of the geometry used in the three-point loading test of one adobe brick. The depth of the brick is 170 mm.

The mechanical properties of adobe greatly depend on how it was made: especially the mixture used, age, and water contents. For example, adobe's Young modulus can range from 10 MPa [23] to 200 MPa [24] (see [chapter 2](#)). Then, instead of trying to perfectly match the experimental measurements, the focus is on reproducing the material behavior. The material properties used for the simulations are listed in [Table 9.3](#). This table also contains the final calibrated parameters: the Young modulus for the beams and their cohesion failing value. For the beam geometric properties, as shown in [Figure 7.1](#), x_i and x_j are zero, and the radii for the beams are equal to the radius of the smaller sphere in the connection. The maximum distance l_0 between grains is $1/3$ of the radius of the smallest sphere in the simulation, in the case of the Voronoï polyhedra, and $1/8$ in the case of the brick made of spheres. Spheres joined by beams can overlap, and two connected spheres cannot experience Hertz forces. The parameters for steel are a Young modulus of $E_s = 200$ GPa, a Poisson ratio of $\nu_s = 0.3$, a density of $\rho_s = 7850$ kg/m³, and friction coefficient of $\mu_s = 0.4$. Gravity in the place of the measurements (National University of Colombia) is 9.77412 m/s² [139].

9.1.1 A Brick of Spheres

Using spheres with 5% polydispersity, we created the adobe brick in [Figure 9.1](#). First, we compared the elastic region of the flexural test for the different samples. Each brick was created four times with different seeds for the random number generator. The reported values are the average of the four measurements. An image of the simulation setup can be seen in [Figure 9.2](#). To create the brick, the spheres were deposited inside a mold with the shape of the brick. The spheres were frictionless to avoid boundary effects. Once the spheres settled down, they were added to the simulation.

Figure 9.2: Simulation setup of adobe bricks with 5% polydispersity spheres. This brick was created with 4961 spheres.

We compare the elastic region of the test with the experimental results. At this point, we do not allow the beams to break. Rayleigh damping ([section 5.4](#)) with a damping fraction of 0.15 was used. [Figure 9.3](#) shows the simulation results compared with the experiments for several sphere sizes, with each one corresponding to a number of spheres N , as summarized in [Table 9.1](#). Smaller spheres mean more spheres. The beam material parameters were the same as adobe ([Table 9.3](#)).

Figure 9.3: Loading force vs. displacement in the three-point flexural test using bricks made of spheres. Experimental results of the same test on adobe bricks with the same dimensions are also available for comparison. The reported value of the simulations is the average of the bricks created with different random seeds, and the light color region is the standard deviation of the data. N denotes the number of spheres used to create the brick.

Figure 9.3 illustrates that the bricks of spheres without calibration do not match the experimental results. To obtain similar results, stiffer beams are necessary. Additionally, it can be seen that increasing the number of spheres in the brick leads to better outcomes, but increasing computational costs. Table 9.1 displays the number of used beams plus the CPU times for each simulation. Also, note that the results of the simulation with 4961 and 2630 are almost equivalent. Then, at least 2630 spheres are required to properly model the brick.

Table 9.1: Number of spheres and beams used to create the bricks for the simulation in Figure 9.3. CPU time corresponds to a simulation with 240000 steps. The simulation was performed in a laptop with CPU Intel i5-1135G7 and 20 Gb RAM. Each simulation was executed in parallel using 2 cores.

Spheres	Beams	CPU time
4961	18143	2 h 42 min
2630	9293	1 h 13 min
763	2474	16 min
315	925	5 min

We can calibrate the results in [Figure 9.3](#) using a brick with 2630 spheres and multiplying the Young modulus of the beams by a constant factor. The results of the calibration are in [Figure 9.4](#). Note that a factor of around 8x is required for reproducing the experimental results.

Figure 9.4: Loading force vs. displacement in the three-point flexural test using bricks of 2630 spheres. Experimental results of the same test on adobe bricks with the same dimensions are also available for comparison. The reported value of the simulations is the average of the bricks created with different random seeds. The legend denotes the multiplying factor used to increase the adobe Young modulus assigned to the beams.

9.1.2 A Brick of Voronoï Polyhedra

In the previous experiment with adobe bricks, we found that it required many spheres and beams to achieve accurate results. To improve performance, we tried a different approach: discretizing the brick into Voronoï polyhedra represented as multi-spheres and connecting with beams only the spheres of two polyhedra intersecting at a common face. To create Voronoï cells with similar dimensions, we distributed uniform points inside the brick and added random displacements, and then we used those points to define the Voronoï cells using the `voronoi3d_cuboid` Matlab subroutine [140]. Next, we used CLUMP [141], a Matlab open-source code, to create the multi-spheres for each cell. Four bricks were created, each with a different random seed, and the reported values are the average of the four measurements. The beam material parameters were the same as the ones reported for adobe. See [Figure 9.5](#) for an image of the simulation setup with Voronoï cells.

Figure 9.5: Simulation setup with adobe bricks made of Voronoi cells and multi-spheres. N denotes the number of Voronoi cells that compose each brick. The bricks are colored by the ID of the cells.

During the loading test, the bricks built from Voronoi cells closely resemble the experimental results without calibration. The results for the bricks with varying numbers of Voronoi tessellations can be found in [Figure 9.6](#). It is clear that, just as with spheres, having more cells brings us closer to experimental behavior. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that bricks with 80, 150, and 252 cells behave similarly, and their results fall well within the standard deviation of each other, as can be seen in the highlighted region of each curve. Adding more cells beyond 80 reduces the standard deviation among bricks created with different random seeds, but not the mean values.

Figure 9.6: Loading force vs. displacement in the three-point flexural test using bricks made of Voronoi cells. Experimental results of the same test on adobe bricks with the same dimensions are also available for comparison. The reported value of the simulations is the average of four bricks created with different random seeds, and the light color region is the standard deviation of the data. N denotes the number of Voronoi cells used to create the brick.

Another benefit of using the bricks with Voronoi cells is the increase in performance that comes with it. Table 9.2 shows the number of spheres and beams plus the CPU times for each simulation. We can see that modeling with Voronoi cells is around 4x faster than with spheres only, see Table 9.1.

Table 9.2: Number of Voronoi cells, spheres, and beams used to create the bricks for the simulation in Figure 9.3. CPU time corresponds to a simulation with 240000 steps. The simulation was performed in a laptop with CPU Intel i5-1135G7 and 20 Gb RAM. Each simulation was executed in parallel using 2 cores.

Cells	Spheres	Beams	CPU Time
252	5040	3826	42 min
150	3000	2991	30 min
80	1600	2474	11 min
36	720	567	4 min

Analyzing the results of Figure 9.6, we still need to calibrate the stiffness of the beams. Then, trying different multiplication factors using a linear range, we can find the one that matches the

expected material properties. In addition, the strain rate was reduced to 0.5 mm/s to increase the accuracy of the measurements and avoid the dynamic oscillations that can be seen in [Figure 9.6](#). Note that the nonlinear region in the loading tests is an artifact from the simulation because the surface of the brick is not smooth. The calibration results can be seen in [Figure 9.7](#). For now on, the value we will use for the beams is the one that corresponds to the $3.5\times$ calibration factor, 63 MPa.

Figure 9.7: Loading force vs. displacement in the three-point flexural test using bricks of 80 Voronoi cells. Experimental results of the same test on adobe bricks with the same dimensions are also available for comparison. The reported value of the simulations is the average of the bricks created with different random seeds. The legend denotes the multiplying factor for the adobe Young modulus assigned to the beams.

An important remark to be noted for calibrating the breakage parameters is that the adobe bricks crack when failing. Therefore, the experimental loading data after failure is not very reliable. Then, we focused on finding the parameters that make the brick fail at the correct point, but not on reproducing the behavior after failing. In addition, we also focused on obtaining the qualitative failing behavior. In [Figure 9.8](#) some pictures of adobe bricks failing in the 3-point test can be seen. [Figure 9.9](#) shows fractured bricks, each one created with a different random seed and Voronoi cell count. Notice how the crack propagates vertically through the material in a similar way as in our simulations.

Figure 9.8: Images of different adobe bricks failing under the 3-point loading test. From them. Pictures display how adobe bricks fail, with vertical cracks all the way down. Pictures were taken by Jhonatan Augusto Forero Pabón.

Figure 9.9: Different fractured bricks created with random seeds and Voronoi cell counts. N denotes the number of Voronoi cells in the brick.

Now that we found the parameters for the beams which reproduce the expected elastic material behavior, and we show that increasing the amount of Voronoi cells above a certain value does not change the results, we go on to calibrate the failure parameters of the beams. Figure 9.10 shows the results of multiple simulations using the previously defined parameters and different values for the cohesion value. To make the material slightly less brittle, we choose the Young modulus of

each beam from a random normal distribution centered around the Young modulus for adobe with a standard deviation of 5%.

Figure 9.10: Loading force vs. displacement in the three-point flexural test using bricks of 80 Voronoï cells. Experimental results of the same test on adobe bricks with the same dimensions are also available for comparison. The reported value of the simulations is the average of the bricks created with different random seeds. The legend denotes the cohesion in the Mohr-Coulomb failure criteria.

The results of the calibration tests can be seen in Figure 9.10(a). Note that the material displays a small amount of plasticity that is impossible to capture in this model. However, the overall behavior of the material is described accurately. After the calibration, the cohesion value used for the upcoming simulations is $c = 0.3$ MPa, which agrees with literature-reported values [142].

A comparison of the behavior of the material with the same parameters but with different numbers of Voronoï cells can be seen in Figure 9.10(b). Some relevant conclusions can be derived from those results. We observed before that with 80 or more cells the elastic behavior remains stable and well within the standard deviation of the measurements. All reported measurements were taken as an average of testing four bricks produced using different seeds for the random number generators. Nevertheless, increasing the number of Voronoï cells reduces the variation in measurements. The more Voronoï cells, the more consistent the failure behavior is. As bricks made of adobe vary significantly with their manufacturing process, the gained disorder from using few cells is a desirable effect. Additionally, using bricks with few cells decreases computational costs. Nonetheless, to obtain a reliable failure behavior, we recommended using bricks with 150 Voronoï cells or more. Note in Figure 9.10(b) that bricks made with 150 cells fail all around the same

displacement of 2mm, whereas bricks with 80 cells fail on a broader displacement range from 1.5 to 2.4mm. Finally, a table containing all the used and calibrated parameters can be seen in [Table 9.3](#).

Table 9.3: Parameters used to reproduce the behavior observed experimentally of the adobe bricks.

Quantity	Value
Adobe Young modulus	18 MPa
Adobe Poisson ratio	0.15
Adobe density	1600 kg/m ³
Adobe - Adobe static friction coefficient	0.6
Adobe restitution coefficient	0.7
Adobe angle of internal friction	25°
Adobe cohesion	0.3 MPa
Beam Young modulus	63 MPa
Beam Young modulus sigma	3.15 MPa
Beam Poisson ratio	0.15
Beam max l_0	$rad_{min}/3$
Beam Rayleigh damping fraction	0.15
Rod loading speed	0.5 mm/s
Time step	10 μs

9.2 Brick Damage Absorption

In this section, we test how the bricks of the previous section absorb damage. We enforce a harmonic oscillation motion in the loading rod to do this. We perform three loading cycles with displacements ranging from 0 to 1.5 mm to prevent the material from fracturing. A maximum loading speed of $A\omega = 1.5$ mm/s was used. [Figure 9.11](#) shows the results of the hysteresis cycle. For the plot, the reference point is shifted such that the center of the range is the origin. Experimental data for this test is not available. Nevertheless, the plot shows that the model with those parameters is not able to capture cumulative damage. The area of each hysteresis cycle is the amount of energy the brick absorbs.

Figure 9.11: Brick Hysteresis test. The reported value is the average of the values obtained in the test using bricks created with different seeds for the random number generator.

In this chapter, we have shown that the elastic behavior and failing threshold of adobe bricks can be accurately modeled with bricks made of Voronoï polyhedra represented with multi-spheres, which was the ultimate goal of the present work. Those bricks are now at the disposal to be used for modeling walls and other structures made from adobe in future research.

Conclusions

In this work, we developed a model to simulate fracture in brittle materials such as adobe. Our model represents the material as a collection of either spheres or Voronoï polyhedra approximated by multi-spheres, both bounded by beam elements to capture the interactions between neighboring spheres. This approach not only preserves all the characteristics of finite element elastic beams but also allows for the implementation of realistic failure criteria, like Mohr-Coulomb, and realistic damping forces, like Rayleigh damping. This feature sets our model apart from many DEM approaches which often rely on simplified force and fracture models. Furthermore, our developed model reproduces quite well the experimentally reported behavior of brittle materials, like adobe [62, 61] or metamaterials made of spheres with hardened glue bridges [47] (see [section 8.3](#)). This work constitutes a valuable contribution to the field, modeling brittle and other materials, and expanding the possibilities for accurate and efficient simulations.

The beam force model introduced in this study connects spheres using elastic beam elements that closely resemble FEM matrix beam elements (see [chapter 5](#) and [chapter 7](#)). Those beam elements accurately capture the material’s elastic behavior and effectively model dynamic fractures, overcoming the limitations associated with mesh-based techniques. Moreover, the model incorporates Rayleigh damping ([section 5.4](#)), which accounts for energy dissipation within the material, leading to more realistic simulations and enhancing stability in dynamic simulations. We also derived analytically the eigenmodes of the beam elements that are used in Rayleigh damping to set the damping frequencies. This is especially useful when no experimental data of the damping as a function of the oscillation frequency is available, improving the model’s flexibility. Additionally, beam elements enable the calculation of principal stresses, allowing the implementation of appropriate failure criteria, like the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion we used. To validate the accuracy of the force model, we compared its results against the analytical solutions of a cantilever and a fixed simply supported beam, where the model performed extremely well. The beam force model we developed was implemented in YADE [43], making it capable of handling simulations involving multiple spheres and parallel computing. Also, due to the way it was implemented, this beam model can be used not just to bond spheres but also clumps (collections of spheres that behave like

non-spherical rigid bodies). We have requested integration of the model in the main YADE release.

As the proposed beam element force depends on three-dimensional displacements and torsions, as well as on 3D linear and angular velocities, an accurate rotational integration algorithm is essential to ensure maximum performance. Thus, we developed a novel integration algorithm for rotational motion (see [section 6.3](#)) that outperforms all the algorithms currently used in state-of-the-art DEM codes like YADE [43], Mercury [41], LIGGGHTS [114], and many more (see [Table 6.1](#)) in all proposed test cases. The test cases include accuracy, numerical stability, performance, and ability to conserve the energy of the simulation. Furthermore, it is a third-order algorithm (when all the algorithms used by the DEM codes are second-order), can be elegantly derived, and can be adapted to programs using leapfrog and non-leapfrog architectures. The new algorithm allows up to three orders of magnitude larger time steps than some of the second-order methods in use due to its superior accuracy and stability; while only taking 50% more computational time per step, achieving impressive performance gains when employing time steps that attain a fixed target error. Moreover, it only requires one force calculation per time step. The new algorithm is so good that could be turned into a new standard in the field. We have successfully integrated this algorithm into YADE [43], and a paper displaying the details of the algorithm has been written and is soon to be submitted. Furthermore, the DEM9 conference, to be held September 17th to 21st in Erlangen (Germany), [46] has accepted the author for an oral presentation on this algorithm.

The flexible implementation of the beam forces allows us to adapt the geometry of the bonds to simulate a wide range of systems. By modeling materials, as a collection of spheres interconnected by beams, we successfully replicated the behavior of a metamaterial with tunable elasticity (see [section 8.3](#)). Specifically, we applied this approach to simulate a metamaterial composed of glass beads connected by hardened glue bridges. Depending on the stiffness of the glue bridges, the Young modulus of the material can vary in a range of three orders of magnitude. By closely replicating the system’s geometry and using the experimental parameters, we reproduced the experimental results with minimal calibration. This result is a good example illustrating the power and possibilities of the beam force model we developed.

With the constructed simulation tools, we successfully conducted simulations of adobe bricks using two different approaches: employing spheres or utilizing Voronoï polyhedra represented by multi-spheres as discrete elements joined by beams (see [chapter 9](#)). In both cases, we accurately captured the elastic behavior of the material. However, by utilizing Voronoï polyhedra represented by multi-spheres, we achieved significant computational performance improvements, with simulation speeds up to four times faster compared to using spheres alone. Notably, our model replicated the fracture behavior of the bricks and is in good agreement with the experimental data. Also, the random nature of the Voronoï polyhedra structure accounts for the variability and heterogeneous composition of adobe bricks.

There is a lot of potential for future work in this work. Testing different failure criteria for the beams, like von Misses, could expand the range of systems that can be simulated to ductile materials. Furthermore, employing a wider range of failure thresholds could be used to capture

material plasticity and cumulative damage. In addition to simulating individual bricks, it is possible to perform simulations of entire adobe walls and assess their structural behavior under seismic loading conditions. Exploring the relationship between the distribution of beam dimensions, material properties, and the macroscopic behavior of the material would provide insights for setting up simulations with this model. All those would be valuable issues for future research.

This study presents a novel model that effectively simulates fracture in brittle continuum materials using spheres and Voronoi polyhedra. The model introduces a flexible implementation of beam forces, allowing for easy adaptation to different systems, and incorporates appropriate failure criteria. A new rotational integration algorithm that demonstrates superior accuracy, stability, and efficiency, with the potential to become a new standard in the field, was developed. The integration algorithm and force model was integrated into YADE and made available to everyone through a merge request.

By using spheres joined by beams, our model was able to accurately reproduce the elastic behavior of a metamaterial composed of glass beads connected by hardened glue bridges. By using either spherical elements or Voronoi polyhedra, we were able to reproduce the elastic and failure behavior of adobe bricks, which was the ultimate goal of this thesis. Nevertheless, This work goes beyond material modeling, contributing to the brittle fracture simulation field. The model accurately captures the geometric and mechanical aspects of the materials, providing both qualitative and quantitative representations of fracture phenomena with improved performance, and constitutes a highly valuable contribution to the field of discrete element fracture modeling and the discrete element method itself.

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